

Supplementary Information

1-Oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane as a New Potential Piperazine Bioisostere - Flow-Assisted Preparation and Derivatisation by Strain-Release of Azabicyclo[1.1.0]butanes

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1. General Information

Solvents, Reagents and Reactions

All chemicals were purchased from commercial suppliers (e.g., Alfa Aesar, Merck, Fluorochem, Fluka, BLDpharm and TCI Europe), and used without further purification unless otherwise specified. Chemical symbols have their usual meaning. SI units and their respective standard symbols are used. Evaporation of solvent was achieved using a Büchi R-300 rotary evaporator under reduced pressure (0 – 1000 mbar) with a bath temperature of 40 °C. Reactions were performed in cooled oven-dried glassware (dried at 85 °C for 12 hrs) under a nitrogen atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. *n*-Butyllithium solution (2.5 M in hexane) was purchased from Merck/Sigma-Aldrich and titrated with diphenylacetic acid before use. *sec*-Butyllithium solution (1.4 M in cyclohexane) was purchased from Merck/Sigma-Aldrich and titrated before use. Hexyllithium solution (2.3 M in hexane) was purchased from Merck/Sigma-Aldrich and titrated before use. THF was distilled from sodium and benzophenone before use. *n*-Hexane was distilled from calcium chloride before use.

Chromatography

Flash column chromatography was performed using 40-63 µm mesh silica (Geduran, Merck) using head pressure achieved by the use of head bellows. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was conducted on aluminium-backed 0.25 mm precoated silica plates with fluorescent indicator (60 F254, Merck) and the spots were visualized under UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm) or by oxidation with KMnO_4 (aq.).

Analysis, Spectroscopy and Spectrometry of compounds

^1H , ^{13}C and ^{19}F NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Ascend-400 spectrometer (400 MHz for ^1H , 101 MHz for ^{13}C , 377 MHz for ^{19}F). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) and referenced to the non-deuterated residual solvent peak. Spin-spin coupling constants (J) are given in Hz. The multiplicity of the signals is reported as s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), quin (quintet), br (broad signal), m (multiplet). Spin-spin coupling constants (J) are given in Hz. As far as possible, assignment of all unambiguous resonances was performed by combined application of 1D and 2D NMR techniques, i.e. HSQC, COSY and HMBC experiments. ^1H NMR on the reaction crude was used to establish the diastereomeric ratio. Thermoscientific Nicolet Summit PRO FTIR Spectrometer was employed to obtain the infrared spectra and samples were loaded neat, and absorption frequencies are recorded in cm^{-1} . Agilent 6530 accurate mass Q-TOF instrument and Excalibur data system were used to record the high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) spectra. GC analyses were performed using a gas chromatograph (dimethylsilicon capillary column, 30 m, 0.25 mm i.d.) equipped with a mass selective detector operating at 70 eV (EI). Quantitative ^1H -NMR yields were calculated using CH_2Br_2 as an internal standard.

Flow set-up:

The continuous flow reactions were performed in R2+ Vapourtec. PTFE tubes (1.0 mmID) (Bola) and T-connectors (PEEK, 1.0 mm through hole) (Idex) were utilized for the synthesis, lithiation and quenching steps. A passive back pressure regulator was used. The flow microreactor system was immersed in a thermostat-bath to control the temperature. Solutions of the reaction components were introduced to the flow microreactor system using 3 x 5 mL loops in PTFE and R2+ Vapourtec. All experiments were set by Flow Commander Software to determine the evolution of the system towards the steady-state regime and operated in automatic collecting mode. All the bottle solvents connected to the system were kept under Argon atmosphere.

2. General procedures

2.1 General procedure 1 (GP1): Synthesis of nitrones

Prepared according to a previously reported procedure.^[1]

To a solution of aldehyde (1 equiv.) and *N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine chloride (1 equiv.) in dichloromethane (0.33 M) was added pyrrolidine (1.2 equiv.) dropwise under stirring at room temperature. The reaction was followed by GC analysis until full conversion of the aldehyde was observed. Upon completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was filtered through a short pad of gel silica (for aromatic nitrones) or basic Al₂O₃ (for α,β -unsaturated nitrones) and washed thoroughly with EtOAc. The filtrate was subsequently concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain the crude nitrones, which were sufficiently pure for further synthetic steps in most cases.

2.2 General procedure 2 (GP2): Synthesis of hydrobromide salt and its free amine

Prepared according to a previously reported procedure.^[2]

Br₂ (10 mL, 0.20 mol, 2.1 equiv) was added dropwise to vigorously stirring ethanol (25 mL) at 0 °C. After complete addition, allylamine (7 mL, 0.09 mol, 1.0 equiv) was added slowly dropwise with a syringe pump (flow rate: 0.232 mL/min) under vigorous stirring at 0 °C. Upon complete addition, the mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred for 16 h, before addition of small portions of ice-cold Et₂O (5 x 10 mL). The resulting precipitate was collected via suction filtration, and then dissolved in the minimum amount of methanol. Then, Et₂O was added dropwise until a white precipitate formed. After complete precipitation, the desired ammonium salt (18 g, 0.054 mol, 60%) was collected as a white solid via suction filtration. The obtained salt can be readily stored at room temperature (for months) without degradation.

The required free amine was prepared ahead of any reaction and directly used, given that degradation/polymerization is observed within 1 hour at room temperature. The hydrogen bromide salt was dissolved in NaOH(aq). (1.0 M, 5 mL per 1 g) under exclusion of light and stirred for 10 minutes. The aqueous phase was subsequently extracted with DCM (3 x 10 mL). The

combined organic layers were dried over Na_2SO_4 and the volatiles were removed under reduced pressure yielding the free amine as a pale yellow oil, which was used for the next reaction.

2.3 General procedure 3 (GP3): Flow synthesis of C3-functionalized ABBs

The process was performed using a Vapourtec R2+ series reactor with two PTFE reactors ($\varnothing_{int}=1.0$ mm) of 2 mL (R₁) and 5 mL (R₂) with a passive back pressure regulator. The system and operative conditions can be displayed as follows:

The solutions were prepared and loaded in PTFE loops as follows:

Loop A, 5 mL, *n*-BuLi 1.6 M in dry hexane (8.0 mmol) [**Solution A**];

Loop B, 5 mL, dibromopropylamine 0.32 M in dry THF (1.6 mmol, 347 mg) [**Solution B**];

Loop C, 5 mL, electrophile 0.3 M in dry THF (1.5 mmol) [**Solution C**].

Solvent bottles containing freshly distilled THF were employed for pushing solutions **B**, and **C** in the system. Solvent bottle containing freshly distilled hexane was employed for pushing solution **A** in the system.

The three solutions were pumped into the system using the following flow rates:

Solution A [*n*-BuLi]: 0.30 mL/min;

Solution B [dibromopropylamine]: 0.50 mL/min;

Solution C [electrophile]: 0.60 mL/min.

The T-mixers and reactors were kept at 0 °C using a thermostated water bath under constant sonication for the reaction duration to prevent clogging. Solutions **A** and **B** were mixed using a PEEK T-shape micromixer ($\phi_{\text{int}}=1.00$ mm). The resulting solution was passed through **R**₁ (2 mL, $t_{\text{R1}}=2.5$ min), and was mixed with solution **C** using a PEEK T-shape micromixer ($\phi_{\text{int}}=1.00$ mm) and introduced in **R**₂ (5 mL, $t_{\text{R2}}=3.5$ min). The resulting solution was collected directly in a stirred flask with water (5 mL), after reaching the steady state (1.4 min) for 6 min & 13 s. The mixture was extracted with DCM (3 × 15 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure. In most cases, the obtained crude was used directly for further steps. The reported yields are calculated by quantitative ¹H-NMR analysis. For unambiguous structural identification, some hydroxylamines were purified by washes with hexane/diethyl ether and fully characterised spectroscopically.

2.4 General procedure 4 (GP4): Batch synthesis of C3-functionalized ABBs

Note: Hydroxylamines **11** and **14** were synthesized according to the following procedure due to reduced productivity in flow.

To a solution of dibromopropylamine (200 mg, 0.92 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in THF (4 mL) cooled to 0 °C was added dropwise a solution of *sec*-butyllithium (1.1 M in cyclohexane, 3.0 mL, 3.3 mmol, 3.6 equiv.). The resulting yellow reaction mixture was allowed to stir for 14 minutes, before the corresponding nitron (1.2 equiv.) was added neat. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir for further 1 hr while allowing to warm to room temperature, before it was diluted with Et₂O (10 mL), and quenched with deionised water (10 mL). The aqueous phase was separated and extracted with Et₂O (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phase was dried with Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain the crude hydroxylamines, which were purified by washes with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 8:2 v/v), or used directly in the next step.

2.5 General procedure 5 (GP5): Boc-induced spirocyclisation for the synthesis of 1-Oxa-2,6 diazapro[3.3]heptane

To a stirred solution of crude hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3** or **GP4** (1.0 equiv) and Boc_2O (1.5 equiv) in DCM (0.1 M), was added Amberlyst 15 (160 mg per mmol of hydroxylamine). After stirring for 16 h at room temperature, the mixture was filtered and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by flash column chromatography.

2.6 General procedure 6 (GP6): TFA-induced spirocyclisation to 1-Oxa-2,6 diazapro[3.3]heptane

To a solution of hydroxylamine (1.0 equiv.) obtained from **GP3** or **GP4** in dichloromethane (0.1 M) at 0 °C was added trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (1.1 equiv.) dropwise. After addition, the mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred for 30 minutes, before being concentrated under reduced pressure. In most cases, the crude material was sufficiently pure to be used directly in subsequent steps. If required, the crude material can be washed with ice-cold hexane/diethyl ether (2 x 10 mL, 9:1 v/v) to obtain the pure title compound.

Note: The salts are slightly soluble in ice-cold hexane/diethyl ether, leading to drops in isolated yields by ca. 10%.

2.7 General procedure 7 (GP7): NH-functionalisation of 1-Oxa-2,6 diazapro[3.3]heptane

To a solution of TFA-adduct (1.0 equiv.) in dichloromethane (0.09 M) cooled to 0 °C was added Et₃N (3.0 equiv.) dropwise. After addition, the reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 5 minutes, before the electrophile (see **4. Electrophile collection**) (1.1 equiv.) was added neat. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and subsequently stirred for 18 hrs. Upon completion of the reaction, deionized water was added. The resulting aqueous phase was separated, and extracted with DCM (3 × 10 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated under reduced pressure. The obtained crude material was purified by flash column chromatography.

2.8 General procedure 8 (GP8): Buchwald-Hartwig coupling

Adapted from a previously reported procedure.^[3]

To a solution of TFA-adduct (1.0 equiv.) in toluene (0.1 M) at room temperature was added aryl bromide (1.0 equiv, see **5. Aryl Bromide collection**), tris(dibenzylideneacetone)dipalladium(0) (3 mol%), Xantphos (6 mol%) and sodium *tert*-butoxide (3.0 equiv) consecutively. The reaction mixture was allowed to stir at 100 °C (oil bath) for 18 h. Upon completion of the reaction, the mixture was allowed to cool to ambient temperature, filtered through a short pad of celite, and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude material was purified by flash column chromatography.

2.9 General procedure 9 (GP9): Synthesis of acyl chlorides

To a solution of carboxylic acid (1.0 equiv.) in hexane (0.43 M), was added thionyl chloride (1.1 equiv) and DMF (5 mol%). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature. Progress of the reaction was monitored by GC until full conversion of the carboxylic acid was observed. Upon completion, distilled water was added (15 mL). The aqueous phase was separated, and extracted with DCM (3 × 10 mL). The combined organic phases were dried over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated

under reduced pressure to obtain the desired acyl chloride, which was used immediately in the next step (**GP7**) without further purification.

2.10 General procedure 10 (GP10): Reduction to C3-aminoalkylazetidinsols.

Prepared according to a previously reported procedure.^[4]

To a glass vial containing a solution of corresponding 1-Oxa-2,6 diazaspiro[3.3]heptane (1.0 equiv.) in EtOH/H₂O (4:1, 0.68 M) was added iron powder (10 equiv.) and ammonium chloride (10 equiv.) consecutively. The resulting suspension was stirred at 70 °C (oil bath) for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, filtered through a short pad of celite and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by flash column chromatography.

3. Nitron collection

Nitrones **A-D**, **G**, **I**, **N** are known compounds. The obtained spectroscopic data matched with those previously reported. **A-C**^[5], **D**^[6], **E**^[7], **F**^[6], **I**^[8], **N**^[9]

4. Electrophile collection

Electrophiles **P-U** are commercially available and were used as received. Electrophiles **V – Y** were obtained through subjecting ibuprofen (**V**) naproxen (**W**), indomethacin (**X**), flurbiprofen (**Y**) to **General Procedure 9**. The obtained spectroscopic data are in agreement with those previously reported: **V**^[10], **W**^[11], **X**^[12]

5. Aryl bromide collection

Aryl bromides **AA-AC** are commercially available and were used as received.

6. Computational data

6.1 Known piperazine bioisosteres

A number of 40 commercially piperazine bioisosteres were taken from the dedicated building block collection available from ENAMINE (<https://enamine.net/building-blocks/medchem/spirocyclic-piperidine-bioisostere>) after removal of the BOC protecting groups. Four additional known biososteres (oxadiazinane and three pyrrole derivatives) and, of course, the piperazine itself were also included.

As a whole, this pool of 45 structures is employed to assess whether the 1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane (termed as *ODASE*) reflects the physicochemical properties of known piperazine bioisosteres.

6.2 Representative cycle-types

Each structure was labelled based on its representative cycle-type (i.e., spiro, bridged, bridged&fused, fused, pyrrole, one-cycle) as shown in Figure 1. The entire list of structures is reported in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Representative structure for each cycle-type.

Figure 2. Piperazine bioisosteres along with their custom label

6.3 3D optimization

Ab-initio calculations were carried out to determine the atomic positions. Structural optimization was conducted using Density Functional Theory (DFT) adopting WB97X-D3BJ as density functional with the 6-31++G(d,p) as basis set. The accuracy of DFT optimization was evaluated by comparison with crystallographic data.

6.4 Local descriptors

Two local descriptors accounting for the spatial relationships of the two nitrogen atoms shared by all the known piperazine biostesters were calculated. The first, termed as “planesNN”, measures the angle formed between the two planes defined by each nitrogen atom with the two adjacent carbon atoms. The second, termed as “distanceN-N”, measures the distance between the two nitrogen atoms.

6.5 Shape evaluation

Molecular shape is commonly evaluated by the normalized principal moments of inertia, defined as:

$$PM_x = \frac{I_x}{I_z}; PM_y = \frac{I_y}{I_z}$$

where I_x , I_y and I_z are the moment of inertia along x, y and z axes, respectively.

The triangle vertices of coordinates (0,1), (0.5, 0.5) and (1,1) represent rod, disc and sphere molecular shapes, respectively.

Figure 3. Scatter plot of normalized principal moments of inertia for each structure colored-based on its cycle-type.

The sum of the normalized principal moments is equal to the 3D score, whose distribution is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Distribution of 3D score.

6.6 Drug-likeness descriptors

The plane of best fit (PBF) quantifies and characterizes the 3D character of molecules. The quantitative estimate of drug likeness (QED) provides an overall measure of drug efficacy.

Figure 5. Distributions of QED and PBF.

6.7 List of molecular descriptors

Table 1. List of molecular descriptors. The star/hash indicates the 2/3 dimensional character.

DESCRIPTORS	DESCRIPTION
QED [*]	Quantitative estimate of drug likeness
3DSCORE [#]	Sum of normalized principal moments of inertia (PMx and PMy)
PBF [#]	Plane of best fit
MW [*]	Molecular weight
MLOGP [*]	LogP of molecule
MR [*]	Molar Refractivity
TPSA [*]	Topological polar surface area derived by polar atoms
VOLUME [#]	Volume occupied by the molecule
NUMHA [*]	Number of Hydrogen Bond Acceptors
NUMHD [*]	Number of Hydrogen Bond Donors
SMR_VSA3 [*]	Molar Refractivity calculated at surface of VdW with 3 Angstrom
IX [#]	Moment of inertia along x-axis

IY[#]	Moment of inertia along y-axis
IZ[#]	Moment of inertia along z-axis
INERTIASHAPE[#]	Value relative to shape derived by inertia moments
ECCENTRICITY[#]	Deviation from spherical shape
N-N[#]	Euclidean distance between the 2 nitrogen atoms
N-N PLANES[#]	Angle between the two planes derived by considering each nitrogen and its 2 alpha carbon atoms
DIPOLE[*]	Dipole moment calculated by DFT

Figure 6. Variance values of 0-1 normalized descriptors.

Figure 7. Logarithmic variance inflation factor of 0-1 normalized descriptors.

6.8 Principal component analysis

Figure 8. Variance and cumulative variance values of each principal component.

Figure 9. Loading values referring of top- three principal components.

6.9 Cluster analysis

Figure 10. Absolute value of the negative outlier factor at distance of one neighbor.

Figure 11. Inertia values of the k-means algorithm varying the number of clusters.

Figure 12. Davies-Bouldin score and dunno metric values of the k-means algorithm.

Figure 13. Blob plot of silhouette values.

Figure 14. Bar plot of differences in mean silhouette values at the increase of the number of clusters.

7. Characterisation of compounds

(Z)-N-tert-Butyl-1-(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)methanimine oxide, F

Prepared following **GP1** from 2,3-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (500 mg, 3.00 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (377 mg, 3.00 mmol). Compound **F** was obtained as a white solid without further purification (695 mg, 2.92 mmol, 97%); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.85 (dd, $J = 8.1, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.98 (s, 1H, NCH), 7.09 (t, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 6.97 (dd, $J = 8.1, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 3.85 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 3.83 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 1.59 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 151.9 (Ar- C_q), 147.4 (Ar- C_q), 125.2 (Ar- C_q), 124.7 (NCH), 124.3 (Ar-C), 120.7 (Ar-C), 114.7 (Ar-C), 71.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 61.4 (OCH_3), 56.0 (OCH_3), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd

for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_3+\text{Na}^+$: 260.1263 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 260.1259. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2974, 2836, 1576, 1474, 1360, 1283, 1126, 1070, 908, 727$.

(Z)-N-tert-Butyl-1-(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methanimine oxide, H

Prepared following **GP1** from 2-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde (500 mg, 2.87 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (360 mg, 2.87 mmol). Compound **H** was obtained as a white solid (500 mg, 2.03 mmol, 71%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.46 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.93 (d, $J = 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCH), 7.71 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.62 (t, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.45 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 1.62 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 132.2 (q, $^5J_{\text{CF}} = 0.9$ Hz, Ar-C), 129.3 (bs, Ar- C_q), 129.1 (bs, Ar-C), 128.6 (q, $^4J_{\text{CF}} = 1.4$ Hz, Ar-C), 127.5 (q, $^2J_{\text{CF}} = 29.8$ Hz, Ar- C_q), 125.9 (q, $^3J_{\text{CF}} = 5.9$ Hz, Ar-C), 124.3 (q, $^1J_{\text{CF}} = 273.8$ Hz, CF_3), 124.9 (bs, NCH), 72.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -58.86 (s, CF_3). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{F}_3\text{NO}+\text{Na}^+$: 268.0925 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 268.0923. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2978, 1454, 1364, 1311, 1291, 1106, 1032, 912, 766, 655$.

(Z)-N-tert-Butyl-1-(3-chlorophenyl)methanimine oxide, J

Prepared following **GP1** from 3-chlorobenzaldehyde (500 mg, 3.55 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (446 mg, 3.55 mmol). Compound **J** was obtained as white solid (670 mg, 3.16 mmol, 89%) by washing the reaction crude with hexane/AcOEt (2 x 8 mL, 9:1 v/v). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.50 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.00 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.52 (s, 1H, NCH), 7.36 – 7.33 (m 2H, Ar-H), 1.61 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 134.7 (Ar- C_q), 132.7 (Ar- C_q), 130.1 (Ar-C), 129.7 (Ar-C), 128.7 (Ar-C), 128.4 (Ar-C), 127.0 (NCH), 71.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$).

HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{ClO}+\text{Na}^+$: 234.0662 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 234.0658. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2937, 2837, 1579, 1414, 1336, 1233, 1124, 1002, 862, 780$.

(Z)-N-tert-Butyl-1-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)methanimine oxide, K

Prepared following **GP1** from 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (500 mg, 2.54 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (318 mg, 2.54 mmol). Compound **K** was obtained as a white solid (601 mg, 2.25 mmol, 88%) by washing the crude material with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10mL, 4:1 v/v). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.65 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 7.46 (s, 1H, NCH), 3.90 (s, 6H, 2 x CH_3), 3.87 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.60 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 153.0 (Ar- C_q), 139.8 (Ar- C_q), 129.9 (Ar- C_q), 126.6 (NCH), 106.3 (Ar-C), 70.9 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 61.0 (OCH_3), 56.2 (2 x OCH_3), 28.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}_4+\text{Na}^+$: 290.1360 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 290.1364. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2937, 2837, 1579, 1414, 1336, 1233, 1124, 1002, 862, 780.

(Z)-N-tert-Butyl-1-(pyridin-3-yl)methanimine oxide, L

Prepared following **GP1** from nicotinaldehyde (500 mg, 4.66 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (586 mg, 4.66 mmol). Compound **L** was obtained as a brown solid without further purification (823 mg, 4.61 mmol, 99%); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.05 (dt, J = 8.1, 1.8 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 8.94 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 8.53 (d, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.56 (s, 1H, NCH), 7.30 (dd, J = 8.1, 4.9 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 1.58 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 150.3 (Ar-C), 150.2 (Ar-C), 134.7 (Ar-C), 127.6 (NCH), 127.0 (Ar- C_q), 123.5 (Ar-C), 71.6 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}+\text{Na}^+$: 201.1004 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 201.1010. IR (film): $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ = 2937, 2837, 1579, 1414, 1336, 1233, 1124, 1002, 862, 780.

(1Z,2E)-N-(tert-Butyl)-2-methyl-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-imine oxide, M

Prepared following **GP1** from (E)-2-methyl-3-phenylacrylaldehyde (500 mg, 3.42 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (428 mg, 3.42 mmol). Compound **M** was obtained as white waxy solid (535 mg, 2.46 mmol, 72%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel R_f = 0.5 (1:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.34 (s, 1H, NCH), 7.36 – 7.22 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.05 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 2.14 (d, J = 1.3 Hz, 3H, CH_3), 1.51 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 137.6 (Ar- C_q), 134.1 (Ar- C_q), 132.5 (Ar-C), 129.6 (2 x Ar-C), 128.2 (Ar-C), 128.1 (2 x Ar-C), 127.2 (NCH), 70.7 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 18.4 (CH_3). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}+\text{Na}^+$: 240.1364 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 240.1364. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2937, 2837, 1579, 1414, 1336, 1233, 1124, 1002, 862, 780.

(Z)-N-tert-Butyl-1-(4-cyanophenyl)methanimine oxide, O

Prepared following **GP1** from 4-formylbenzonitrile (500 mg, 3.81 mmol) and N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride (478 mg, 3.81 mmol). Compound **O** was obtained as an orange solid without further purification. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.37 (d, J = 8.4, 2H, Ar-H), 7.68 (d, J = 8.4, 2H, Ar-H), 7.61 (s, 1H, NCH), 1.62 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 135.1 (Ar- C_q), 132.3 (2 x Ar-C), 128.8 (2 x Ar-C), 128.4 (NCH), 118.8 (CN), 112.8 (Ar- C_q), 72.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}+\text{Na}^+$: 225.1004 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 225.0994. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2982, 2223, 1736, 1372, 1234, 1043, 841, 634.

***N*-((1-Azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine, 1**

Prepared following **GP3** using *N*-*tert*-butyl-1-phenylmethanimine oxide **A**. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 4:1 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.48 – 7.46 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.31 – 7.25 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 4.89 (s, 1H, OH), 4.47 (s, 1H, NCH), 2.38 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 2.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.14 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 2.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.30 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.12 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.07 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 139.4 (Ar-C_q), 129.7 (2 x Ar-C), 128.1 (2 x Ar-C),

127.5 (Ar-C), 64.0 (NCH), 59.8 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.4 (NCH₂), 52.7 (NCH₂), 33.0 (NC_q), 26.9 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₄H₂₀N₂O+H⁺: 233.1654 [*M*+H]⁺; found 233.1646. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3308, 2971, 2939, 1493, 1452, 1360, 1216, 760, 704.

Spectroscopic data are in agreement with those reported in literature.^[13]

***N*-((1-Azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(3-chlorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine, 2**

Prepared following **GP3** using *N*-*tert*-butyl-1-(3-chlorophenyl)methanimine oxide **J**. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 4:1 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.53 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.35 – 7.32 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.24 – 7.22 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 4.90 (br, 1H, OH), 4.43 (s, 1H, NCH), 2.36 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.11 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.32 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.14 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 2H, NCHH), 1.08 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 141.4 (Ar-C_q), 133.8 (Ar-C_q), 129.4 (Ar-C),

129.3 (Ar-C), 127.7 (Ar-C), 127.6 (Ar-C), 63.6 (NCH), 59.8 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.6 (NCH₂), 52.5 (NCH₂), 32.5 (NC_q), 26.8 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₄H₁₉ClN₂O+Na⁺: 289.1084 [*M*+Na]⁺; found 289.1073. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3289, 2969, 2872, 1571, 1360, 1215, 707.

***N*-((1-Azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine, 3**

Prepared following **GP3** using *N*-*tert*-butyl-1-(4-fluorophenyl)methanimine oxide **D**. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 9:1 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.45 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 5.6 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 6.99 (t, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 4.89 (s, 1H, OH), 4.47 (s, 1H, NCH), 2.34 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.12 (dd, *J* = 6.6, 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.30 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.13 (d, *J* = 2.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.06 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 162.0 (d, ¹*J*_{CF} = 245.8 Hz, CF), 134.9 (d, ⁴*J*_{CF} = 3.3 Hz, Ar-C_q), 131.0 (d, ³*J*_{CF} = 7.8 Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 114.7 (d, ²*J*_{CF} = 21.0 Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 63.0 (NCH), 59.6 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.2 (NCH₂), 52.4 (NCH₂), 32.8 (NC_q), 26.7 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR**

(376.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -115.12 – -115.22 (m). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₄H₁₉FN₂O+Na⁺: 273.1379 [*M*+Na]⁺; found 273.1369. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3309, 2971, 2875, 1602, 1506, 1360, 1220, 839.

(E)-N-(1-(1-Azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)-3-phenylallyl)-N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine, 4

Prepared following **GP3** using *(1E,2E)-N-(tert-butyl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-imine oxide N*. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 4:1 v/v). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.40 – 7.37 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.33 – 7.29 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.25 – 7.21 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 6.59 (dd, $J = 16.3, 8.0$ Hz, 1H, CH=CHCH), 6.50 (d, $J = 16.3$ Hz, 1H, CH=CHCH),) 5.17 (s, 1H, OH), 4.18 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H, NCH), 2.44 (dd, $J = 6.5, 2.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.38 (dd, $J = 6.5, 2.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.30 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 2H, NCHH and NCHH), 1.18 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 137.1 (Ar-C_q), 132.1 (Ar-CH=CH,

128.6 (ArCH=CH), 127.5 (Ar-C), 126.4 (2 x Ar-C), 126.0 (2 x Ar-C), 61.6 (NCH), 59.3 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.3 (NCH₂), 52.3 (NCH₂), 33.2 (NC_q), 27.0 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₁₆H₂₂N₂O+H⁺: 259.1810 [M+H]⁺; found 259.1817. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3275, 3058, 2968, 2872, 1598, 1449, 1359, 1213, 972, 750, 694$.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 5

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine* obtained from **GP3**. Compound **5** was obtained as a white solid (0.27 g, 0.81 mmol, 54% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.47 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.41 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.36 – 7.32 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 4.91 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.21 (dd, $J = 10.7, 1.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.06 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.90 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.65 (d, $J = 11.2$ Hz, 1H,

NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.07 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.3 (C=O), 137.3 (Ar-C_q), 129.0 (2 x Ar-C), 128.6 (Ar-C), 127.6 (2 x Ar-C), 80.9 (OC(CH₃)₃), 79.9 (spiro-C_q), 68.2 (NCH), 62.8 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 59.0 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₁₉H₂₈N₂O₃+Na⁺: 355.1998 [M+Na]⁺; found 355.2003. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2974, 2934, 1704, 1478, 1455, 1393, 1366, 1173, 1100, 898, 766, 700$.

Spectroscopic data are in agreement with those reported in literature.^[13]

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 6

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-chlorophenyl)methyl)-N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine* obtained from **GP3**. Compound **6** was obtained as a white solid (436 mg, 1.18 mmol, 79% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.2$ (9:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.43 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.39 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 4.87 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.20 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.04 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.89 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.61 (d, $J = 10.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.05 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.2

(C=O), 135.9 (Ar-C_q), 134.5 (Ar-C_q), 129.2 (2 x Ar-C), 128.9 (2 x Ar-C), 80.7 (OC(CH₃)₃), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 67.5 (NCH), 62.6 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 58.8 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.3 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₁₉H₂₇ClN₂O₃+Na⁺: 389.1608 [M+Na]⁺; found 389.1614. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2972, 2930, 1698, 1490, 1387, 1364, 1218, 1170, 1090, 838, 771$.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(3-chlorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 7

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(3-chlorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **7** was obtained as a white solid (0.26 g, 0.70 mmol, 48% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel R_f = 0.3 (9:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.53 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.39 – 7.31 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 4.89 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.22 (dd, J = 10.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.06 (dd, J = 10.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.92 (dd, J = 10.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.64 (dd, J = 10.8, 1.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.38 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.08 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.2 (C=O), 139.4 (Ar- C_q), 135.1 (Ar- C_q), 130.3 (Ar-C), 128.9 (Ar-C), 127.7 (Ar-C), 125.6 (Ar-C), 80.8 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 67.6 (NCH), 62.8 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.9 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{27}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 389.1608 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 389.1601. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2973, 2932, 1697, 1476, 1383, 1170, 1098, 784, 684, 608.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 8

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **8** was obtained as a white solid (0.24 g, 0.71 mmol, 47% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel R_f = 0.2 (9:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.47 (td, J = 8.6, 5.4 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.10 (t, J = 8.6, 2H, Ar-H), 4.88 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.20 (dd, J = 10.7, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.04 (dd, J = 10.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.90 (dd, J = 10.7, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.62 (dd, J = 10.7, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.06 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 162.9 (d, $^1J_{\text{CF}}$ = 247.3 Hz, Ar-C_q), 156.2 (C=O), 133.2 (d, $^4J_{\text{CF}}$ = 3.1 Hz, Ar-C_q), 129.3 (d, $^3J_{\text{CF}}$ = 8.2 Hz, Ar-C), 115.9 (d, $^2J_{\text{CF}}$ = 21.6 Hz, Ar-C), 80.8 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 80.0 (spiro-C_q), 67.6 (NCH), 62.7 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.8 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -113.40 – -113.47 (m, F). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{27}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 373.1903 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 373.1905. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2926, 2854, 1704, 1604, 1509, 1390, 1171, 1099, 841, 771.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(2-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 9

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(2-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **9** was obtained as a white solid (0.27 g, 0.77 mmol, 52% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel R_f = 0.4 (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.80 (td, J = 7.5, 1.6 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.35 – 7.28 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.23 (td, J = 7.5, 0.9 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.11 – 7.05 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 5.24 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.24 – 4.17 (m, 2H, NCH₂), 3.90 (d, J = 11.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.69 (d, J = 11.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.39 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.09 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.8 (d, $^1J_{\text{CF}}$ = 245.5 Hz, Ar-C_q), 156.3 (C=O), 129.8 (d, $^3J_{\text{CF}}$ = 8.1 Hz, Ar-C), 129.4 (d, $^3J_{\text{CF}}$ = 3.9 Hz, Ar-C), 124.8

(d, $^4J_{CF} = 3.5$ Hz, Ar-C overlapping Ar- C_q), 115.2 (d, $^2J_{CF} = 20.7$ Hz, Ar-C) 81.0 (OC(CH₃)₃), 79.9 (spiro-C_q), 62.5 (bs, NCH₂), 61.3 (d, $^3J_{CF} = 2.0$ Hz, NCH), 59.3 (NC(CH₃)₃), 59.0 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.3 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -118.46 – -118.97 (bs, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₉H₂₇FN₂O₃ + Na⁺ : 373.1903 [M+Na]⁺; found 373.1901. **IR (film, cm⁻¹)**: ν_{max} = 2965, 2925, 2853, 1707, 1488, 1455, 1389, 1365, 1173, 1093, 902, 760.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 10

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *tert-butyl N-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine* obtained from **GP3**. Compound **10** was obtained as a white solid (0.24 g, 0.59 mmol, 41% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.4 (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.68 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.62 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 4.96 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.23 (dd, *J* = 10.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.08 (dd, *J* = 10.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.90 (dd, *J* = 10.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.56 (dd, *J* = 10.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.82 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.69 (d, *J* = 10.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.07 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.2 (C=O), 141.3 (Ar-C_q), 130.8 (q, $^2J_{CF} = 32.5$ Hz, Ar-C_q), 127.9 (Ar-C), 126.0 (q, $^3J_{CF} = 3.7$ Hz, Ar-C), 124.1 (q, $^1J_{CF} = 272.2$ Hz, CF₃), 80.7 (OC(CH₃)₃), 80.2 (spiro-C_q), 67.6 (NCH), 62.8 (bs, NCH₂), 59.3 (NC(CH₃)₃), 58.9 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.3 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -62.60 (s, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₀H₂₇F₃N₂O₃ + Na⁺: 423.1871 [M+Na]⁺; found 423.1871. **IR (film, cm⁻¹)**: ν_{max} = 2976, 2873, 1703, 1478, 1391, 1366, 1324, 1165, 1127, 851, 769.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 11

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-N-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine* obtained from **GP3**. Compound **11** was obtained as a white solid (0.36 g, 0.89 mmol, 60% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.3 (9:1 hexane/AcOEt). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.34 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.66 – 7.65 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.42 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 5.29 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.16 (s, 2H, NCH₂), 3.81 (d, *J* = 11.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.44 (d, *J* = 11.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.34 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.03 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.1 (C=O), 135.8 (Ar-C_q), 132.7 (Ar-C), 130.7 (Ar-C), 128.4 (Ar-C), 127.3 (q, $^2J_{CF} = 30.1$ Hz, Ar-C_q), 125.8 (q, $^4J_{CF} = 5.7$ Hz, Ar-C), 124.2 (q, $^1J_{CF} = 276.2$ Hz, CF₃), 81.5 (OC(CH₃)₃), 79.8 (spiro-C_q), 63.0 (NCH), 62.5 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 58.6 (bs, NCH₂), 28.3 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.2 (NC(CH₃)₃).

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -58.94 (s, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₀H₂₇F₃N₂O₃ + Na⁺: 423.1871 [M+Na]⁺; found 423.1859. **IR (film, cm⁻¹)**: ν_{max} = 2974, 2873, 1705, 1388, 1365, 1313, 1163, 1112, 1034, 771.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 12

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **12** was obtained as a white solid (0.21 g, 0.52 mmol, 35% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.5$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.76 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.69 (d, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.62 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.55 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 4.96 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.23 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.08 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.91 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.56 (dd, $J = 10.8, 0.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.07 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.2 (C=O), 138.5 (Ar-C_q), 131.5 (q, $^2J_{\text{CF}} = 32.5$ Hz, Ar-C_q), 131.0 (Ar-C), 129.6 (Ar-C), 124.1 (q, $^1J_{\text{CF}} = 272.4$ Hz, CF_3), 125.5 (q, $^3J_{\text{CF}} = 3.7$ Hz, Ar-C), 124.3 (q, $^3J_{\text{CF}} = 3.8$ Hz, Ar-C), 80.7 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 80.2 (spiro-C_q), 67.7 (NCH), 62.8 (bs, NCH₂), 59.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.8 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.5 (s, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{27}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 423.1871 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 423.1870. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2975, 2933, 1698, 1388, 1325, 1163, 1124, 1093, 1074, 703$.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(4-heptanoylphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 13

Prepared following modified **GP4**, followed by **GP5**. To a solution of dibromopropylamine (0.20 g, 0.92 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in THF (4 mL) cooled to 0 °C was added dropwise a solution of *sec*-butyllithium (1.1 M in cyclohexane, 3.0 mL, 3.3 mmol, 3.6 equiv.). The resulting yellow reaction mixture was allowed to stir for 14 minutes, before the corresponding (*Z*)-*N*-tert-butyl-1-(4-cyanophenyl)methanimine oxide (223 mg, 1.10 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was added neat. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir for further 1 hr at 0 °C, before a solution of hexyllithium (2.3 M in hexane, 0.5 mL, 1.1 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred for further 1 hr,

before it was diluted with Et_2O (10 mL), and quenched with deionised water (10 mL). The aqueous phase was separated and extracted with Et_2O (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phase was dried with Na_2SO_4 , filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain the crude hydroxylamine which was used in the next step without further purification. The crude mixture was subsequently subjected to **GP5**. Compound **13** was obtained as a colourless film (0.15 g, 0.34 mmol, 38% over two steps) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.4$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.00 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H, Ar-C), 7.58 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, Ar-C), 4.96 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.21 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.08 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.2$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.90 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.58 (d, $J = 10.7, 1\text{H}$, NCHH), 2.97 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H, COCH_2), 1.78 – 1.71 (m, 2H, COCH_2CH_2), 1.37 – 1.31 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ overlapping m, 6H, 3 x CH_2), 1.07 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 0.90 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H, CH_2CH_3). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 200.2 ($\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$), 156.1 (C=O), 142.1 (Ar-C_q), 137.3 (Ar-C_q), 128.7 (2 x Ar-C), 127.7 (2 x Ar-C), 80.7 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 67.8 (NCH), 62.7 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.9 (bs, NCH₂), 38.8 ($\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$), 31.8 (CH_2), 29.1 (CH_2) 28.3 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 24.4 (CH_2) 23.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 22.6 (CH_2), 14.1 (CH_3). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4 + \text{Na}^+$: 467.2886 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 467.2876. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2959, 2929, 2869, 1685, 1608, 1398, 1384, 1170, 1097, 856, 771$.

tert*-Butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **14*

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(pyridin-3-yl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP4**. Compound **14** was obtained as a white solid (45 mg, 0.13 mmol, 55% over two steps **GP4** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (9:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.64 (d, $J = 1.8$ Hz, 1H, Ar-C), 8.62 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.7$ Hz, 1H, Ar-C), 7.93 (dt, $J = 7.9, 1.8$ Hz, 1H, Ar-C), 7.38 (ddd, $J = 7.8, 4.8, 0.5$ Hz, 1H, Ar-C), 4.94 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.23 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.03 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.94 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.63 (dd, $J = 10.8, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.06 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.1 (C=O), 150.2 (Ar-C), 149.0 (Ar-C), 135.7 (Ar-C), 133.0 (Ar-C_q), 123.9 (Ar-C), 80.6 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 65.9 (NCH), 62.6 (bs, NCH₂), 59.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.7 (bs, NCH₂), 28.3 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 356.1950 [$M + \text{Na}$]⁺; found 356.1938. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2972, 2931, 2870, 1699, 1380, 1364, 1215, 1169, 1097, 714$.

tert*-Butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, **15*

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *tert*-butyl *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-methoxyphenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **15** was obtained as a white solid (0.20 g, 0.55 mmol, 37% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.39 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 6.93 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 4.84 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.19 (dd, $J = 10.7, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.03 (dd, $J = 10.7, 1.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.91 (dd, $J = 10.7, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.82 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 3.69 (d, $J = 10.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.05 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.2 (C=O), 132.1 (Ar-C_q), 129.4 (Ar-C_q), 128.8 (2 x Ar-C), 114.3 (2 x Ar-C), 81.0 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 79.8 (spiro-C_q), 67.8 (NCH), 62.5 (bs, NCH₂), 59.1 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.9 (bs, NCH₂), 55.4 (OCH_3), 28.3 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4 + \text{Na}^+$: 385.2103 [$M + \text{Na}$]⁺; found 385.2095. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2972, 2934, 1698, 1512, 1387, 1364, 1245, 1169, 899, 836, 772$.

tert*-Butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, **16*

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP4**. Compound **16** was obtained as a white waxy solid (0.12 g, 0.32 mmol, 49% over two steps **GP4** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.38 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.11 (t, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 6.90 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 5.26 (bs, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.20 (s, 2H, NCH₂), 3.88 – 3.85 (m, 7H, 2 x CH₃ overlapping 1H, NCHH), 3.69 (d, $J = 10.9$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.38 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.08 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 152.1 (C=O), 145.8 (Ar-C_q), 124.5 (Ar-C_q), 124.2 (Ar-C), 120.5 (Ar-C), 119.6 (Ar-C_q),

112.5 (Ar-C), 81.2 (OC(CH₃)₃), 79.7 (spiro-C_q), 62.5 (NCH), 62.4 (NCH₂), 60.6 (CH₃), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 56.4 (bs, NCH₂), 55.9 (CH₃) 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₁H₃₂N₂O₅ + Na⁺ : 415.2209 [M+Na]⁺; found 415.2204. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 2971, 2870, 1703, 1479, 1280, 1170, 1083, 1008, 905, 771.

tert-Butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 17

Prepared following **GP5** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)methyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **17** was obtained as a white solid (0.26 g, 0.62 mmol, 42% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.2 (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.68 (s, 2 x Ar-H), 4.82 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.19 (d, *J* = 10.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.05 (d, *J* = 10.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.87 (s, 6H, 2 x CH₃ overlapping 1H, NCHH), 3.85 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.67 (d, *J* = 11 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.06 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.2 (C=O), 153.8, 137.9 (Ar-C_q), 133.0 (Ar-C_q), 104.1 (2 x Ar-C),

80.8 (OC(CH₃)₃), 80.0 (spiro-C_q), 68.3 (NCH), 62.6 (NCH₂), 61.0 (CH₃), 59.1 (NC(CH₃)₃), 58.9 (bs, NCH₂), 56.4 (2 x CH₃) 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₁H₃₂N₂O₅ + Na⁺: 445.2315 [M+Na]⁺; found 445.2305. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 2971, 2870, 1703, 1479, 1280, 1170, 1083, 1008, 905, 771.

tert-Butyl (E)-2-(tert-butyl)-3-(1-phenylprop-1-en-2-yl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 18

Prepared following **GP5** from crude (*E*)-*N*-(1-(1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)-2-methyl-3-phenylallyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **18** was obtained as a white solid (0.34 g, 0.91 mmol, 61% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.2 (9:1 hexane/AcOEt). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.31 (m, 4H, Ar-C), 7.24 – 7.23 (m, 1H, Ar-C), 6.86 (s, 1H, Ar-CH=C), 4.38 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.20 (dd, *J* = 11.1, 1.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.11 (d, *J* = 10.2, 1H, NCHH), 4.03 (d, *J* = 10.6 Hz, 2H, 2 x NCHH), 1.96 (d, *J* = 1.3 Hz, 3H, CCH₃), 1.41 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.09 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.4 (C=O), 137.2, 133.7, 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 129.0 (C=CH), 128.4 (2 x Ar-C), 127.0 (Ar-C), 80.6

(OC(CH₃)₃), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 70.6 (NCH), 63.1 (bs, NCH₂), 59.3 (bs, NCH₂), 59.1 (NC(CH₃)₃), 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃), 16.0 (CH₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₂H₃₂N₂O₃ + Na⁺: 395.2311 [M+Na]⁺; found 395.2305. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 2973, 2930, 1699, 1433, 1387, 1217, 1167, 1096, 906, 862.

tert-Butyl (E)-2-(tert-butyl)-3-styryl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate and tert-Butyl (Z)-2-(tert-butyl)-3-styryl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate, 19

Prepared following **GP5** from crude (*E*)-*N*-(1-(1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)-3-phenylallyl)-*N*-(tert-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3**. Compound **19 (E-isomer)** was obtained as a colourless film (47 mg, 0.13 mmol, 13% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.2 (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.43 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.35 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.30 – 7.27 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 6.69 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 1H, Ar-CH), 6.49 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-CHCH), 4.51 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.28 (d, *J* = 10.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.17 (dd, *J* = 10.7, 1.3 Hz,

1H, NCHH), 4.09 (dd, $J = 10.7, 1.0$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.01 (dd, $J = 10.7, 1.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.40 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.09 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.2 (C=O), 136.0 (Ar-C_q), 134.9 (Ar-CH=CH), 128.9 (Ar-C), 128.5 (Ar-C), 126.9 (Ar-C), 125.5 (Ar-CH=CH), 80.6 (OC(CH₃)₃), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 66.7 (NCH), 62.6 (bs, NCH₂), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 59.0 (bs, NCH₂), 28.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₂₁H₃₀N₂O₃+Na⁺: 381.2154 [$M+Na$]⁺; found 381.2152. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{max} = 2973, 2929, 1699, 1452, 1388, 1384, 1149, 1088, 968, 747, 696$.

Compound **19 (Z-isomer)** was obtained as a colourless film (120 mg, 0.33 mmol, 35% over two steps **GP3** and **GP5**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (4:1 hexane/AcOEt). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37 – 7.32 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 6.03 (dd, $J = 9.6, 2.1$ Hz, 1H, Ar-CHCH), 5.93 (dd, $J = 9.6, 1.6$ Hz, 1H, Ar-CH), 5.22 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.53 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.41 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.92 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.84 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.46 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.34 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.6 (C=O), 138.9 (Ar-C_q), 134.4 (CH=CH-Ar), 128.4 (Ar-C), 128.3 (Ar-C), 128.1 (Ar-C), 128.0 (CH=CH-Ar), 79.9 (OC(CH₃)₃), 79.1 (spiro-C_q), 61.1 (NCH), 60.4 (NCH₂), 58.9 (NC(CH₃)₃), 58.2 (bs, NCH₂), 28.5 (OC(CH₃)₃), 28.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₂₁H₃₀N₂O₃+Na⁺: 381.2154 [$M+Na$]⁺; found 381.2152. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{max} = 2973, 2929, 1699, 1452, 1388, 1384, 1149, 1088, 968, 747, 696$.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-ium 2,2,2-trifluoroacetate, 20

Prepared following **GP6** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine obtained from **GP3** or **GP4**. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 8:2 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.61 – 7.58 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.51 – 7.47 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.44 – 7.40 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 5.22 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.49 (d, $J = 12.9$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.38 (d, $J = 12.7$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.15 (d, $J = 12.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.84 (d, $J = 12.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.08 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 162.2 (q, $^2J = 35.2$ Hz, CF₃COO), 137.5 (Ar-C_q),

130.2 (2 x Ar-C), 130.1 (Ar-C), 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 83.4 (NCH), 68.4 (spiro-C_q), 60.4 (NCH₂), 59.4 (NCH₂), 57.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.5 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD) δ -77.03 (s). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₁₄H₂₀N₂O +H⁺: 233.1654 [$M+H$]⁺; found 233.1662. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{max} = 2961, 2929, 2874, 1681, 1449, 1201, 1144, 836, 724, 691$.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-ium 2,2,2-trifluoroacetate, 21

Prepared following **GP6** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-chlorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 8:2 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.58 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.48 (d, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 5.21 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.50 (d, $J = 12.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.37 (d, $J = 12.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.13 (d, $J = 12.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.80 (d, $J = 12.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.05 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 162.4 (q, $^2J = 37.6$ Hz, CF₃COO), 136.3 (Ar-C_q), 135.9 (Ar-C_q), 130.7 (2 x Ar-C), 130.3 (2 x Ar-C), 117.8 (q, $^1J = 289.5$ Hz, CF₃), 83.3 (NCH), 67.5 (spiro-C_q), 60.4 (NCH₂), 59.4

(NCH₂), 57.0 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD) δ -77.01 (bs, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for C₁₄H₁₉ClN₂O +H⁺: 267.1264 [$M+H$]⁺; found 267.1260. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** $\nu_{max} = 2973, 2661, 1671, 1491, 1192, 1180, 1091, 837, 722$.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-ium 2,2,2-trifluoroacetate, **22**

Prepared following **GP6** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-methoxyphenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 8:2 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.50 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.48 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 5.14 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.45 (d, *J* = 12.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.36 (d, *J* = 12.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.15 (d, *J* = 12.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.89 (d, *J* = 12.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.82 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 1.06 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 162.3 (q, ²*J* = 32.9 Hz, CF₃COO), 130.5 (2 x Ar-C), 129.3 (Ar-C_q), 129.0 (Ar-C_q), 117.8 (q, ¹*J* = 292.9 Hz, CF₃), 115.5 (2 x Ar-C), 83.5 (NCH), 68.1 (spiro-C_q), 60.4 (NCH₂), 59.4 (NCH₂), 57.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.8 (CH₃), 23.5 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD) δ -77.08 (bs, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₅H₂₂N₂O₂ + H⁺: 263.1760 [*M*+H]⁺; found 263.1747. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** ν_{max} = 2968, 1672, 1612, 1514, 1250, 1179, 1136, 1031, 936.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-ium 2,2,2-trifluoroacetate, **23**

Prepared following **GP6** from crude *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine. Isolated sample with suitable purity for characterization was obtained after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 8:2 v/v). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.61 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 5.4 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.21 (t, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 5.21 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.48 (d, *J* = 12.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.37 (d, *J* = 12.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.14 (d, *J* = 12.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.82 (d, *J* = 12.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.05 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 164.4 (d, ¹*J* = 246.6 Hz, Ar-C_q), 162.1 (q, ²*J* = 35.6 Hz, CF₃COO), 133.6 (d, ⁴*J* = 3.1 Hz, Ar-C_q), 131.2 (d, ³*J* = 8.4 Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 116.9 (d, ²*J* = 21.9 Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 117.7 (q, ¹*J* = 292.9 Hz, CF₃), 83.3 (d, ⁵*J* = 1.5 Hz, NCH), 67.6 (spiro-C_q), 60.4 (NCH₂), 59.4 (NCH₂), 57.1 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.5 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD) δ -77.19 (s, 3F), -114.79 – -114.87 (m, 1F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₄H₁₉FN₂O + H⁺: 251.1560 [*M*+H]⁺; found 251.1682. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** ν_{max} = 2975, 2663, 1673, 1511, 1439, 1365, 1200, 1180, 840, 722.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-6-tosyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane, **24**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.43 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 4-toluenesulfonyl chloride **R** (90 mg, 0.47 mmol)). Compound **24** was obtained as a white solid (73 mg, 0.18 mmol, 42% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.2 (1:4 EtOAc/hexane). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.59 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.34 – 7.29 (m, 7H, Ar-H), 4.80 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 3.98 (d, *J* = 10.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.92 (d, *J* = 10.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.63 (d, *J* = 10.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.54 (d, *J* = 10.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.44 (s, 3H, ArCH₃), 0.99 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 144.3 (Ar-C_q), 136.5 (Ar-C_q), 130.5 (2 x Ar-C), 129.9 (2 x Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar-C), 128.5 (Ar-C_q), 128.5 (2 x Ar-C), 127.2 (2 x Ar-C), 79.3 (spiro-C_q), 67.9 (NCH), 63.6 (NCH₂), 59.9 (NC(CH₃)₃), 59.0 (NCH₂), 23.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 21.7 (Ar-CH₃). **HRMS** (ESI+)

m/z calcd for $C_{21}H_{26}N_2O_3S + Na^+$: 409.1562 $[M+Na]^+$; found 409.1553. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2971, 2926, 1597, 1344, 1161, 1090, 910, 725, 675.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-6-((3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)sulfonyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane, 25

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine (0.59 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 4-toluenesulfonyl chloride **R** (124 mg, 0.65 mmol)). Compound **25** was obtained as a white solid (0.17 g, 0.39 mmol, 66% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (1:4 EtOAc/hexane). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.72 (bs, 1H, Ar-H), 7.62 – 7.60 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.56 – 7.49 (m,

2H, Ar-H), 7.32 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 4.90 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.00 (d, J = 9.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.91 (dd, J = 9.8, 1.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.61 (d, dd, J = 9.8, 1.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.46 (d, J = 9.8, 1.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.45 (s, 3H, ArCH₃), 1.01 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 144.6 (Ar-C_q), 137.8 (Ar-C_q), 131.4 (q, 2J = 32.5 Hz, Ar-C_q), 130.8 (Ar-C), 130.0 (2 x Ar-C), 129.6 (Ar-C), 128.6 (2 x Ar-C), 126.73 (q, 1J = 274.3 Hz, CF₃), 125.6 (q, 4J = 3.6 Hz, Ar-C), 114.2 (q, 3J = 3.8 Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 79.1 (spiro-C_q), 67.4 (NCH), 63.6 (NCH₂), 59.8 (NC(CH₃)₃), 59.3 (NCH₂), 23.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 21.7 (Ar-CH₃). ^{19}F NMR (376.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ -62.55 (s, F). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $C_{21}H_{23}F_3N_2O_3S + Na^+$: 463.1279 $[M+Na]^+$; found 477.1426. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 2973, 1597, 1451, 1327, 1269, 1162, 1125, 1072, 814.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-6-(*N*-tritylsulfonylimidoyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane, 26

Prepared according to an adapted literature procedure.^[14] To a solution of TrNSO (50.0 mg, 0.164 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in THF (1 mL) cooled to 0 °C was added dropwise phenyllithium solution (1.9 M in dibutyl ether, 0.09 mL, 0.164 mmol, 1.0 equiv) and the resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 5 min at 0 °C. *tert*-Butyl hypochlorite (19.5 μ L, 0.172 mmol, 1.05 equiv.) was then added and the mixture stirred for 15 mins, prior to addition of a solution of 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-ium 2,2,2-trifluoroacetate **20** (85 mg, 0.25 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) and Et₃N (0.09 mL, 0.66 mmol, 4.0 equiv.) in THF (1 mL). After addition, the reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room

temperature and stirred for 18 hours, before it was quenched with saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (5 mL). The aqueous phase was separated and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 x 10 mL). The combined organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford the crude material, which was purified by flash column chromatography (7:3 hexane/EtOAc) to afford the title compound **26** as a white solid as an inseparable mixture of diastereomers (0.18 g, 0.29 mmol, 61%, ca. 55:45). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.83 – 7.10 (m, 50H, Ar-H)^{M+m}, 4.61 (s, 1H, Ar-CH)^M, 4.54 (s, 1H, Ar-CH)^m, 3.62 (d, J = 10.1 Hz, 1H, NCHH)^M, 3.54 – 3.49 (m, 1H, NCHH^M overlapping 1H, NCHH^m), 3.42 (dd, J = 10.1, 1.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH)^m, 3.32 (d, J = 9.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH)^m, 3.30 – 3.24 (m, 1H, NCHH^M overlapping 1H, NCHH^m), 3.15 (d, J = 10.1 Hz, 1H, NCHH)^M, 0.94 (s, 18H, NC(CH₃)₃)^{M+m}. $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 148.0 (3 x Ar-C_q)^m, 147.7 (3 x Ar-C_q)^M, 136.9 (Ar-C_q), 136.8 (Ar-C_q), 136.7 (Ar-C_q), 136.3 (Ar-C_q), 132.0 (Ar-C), 131.8 (Ar-C), 129.3 (Ar-C), 129.2 (Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar-C), 128.4 (Ar-C), 128.4 (Ar-C), 128.3 (Ar-C), 128.1 (Ar-C), 128.0 (Ar-C), 127.4 (Ar-C), 127.3 (Ar-C), 126.4 (Ar-C), 126.4 (Ar-C), 78.8 (spiro-C_q)^M, 78.5 (spiro-C_q)^m, 71.8 (NCH)^m, 71.7 (NCH)^M, 68.0 (NC(CH₃)₃)^M, 68.0 (NC(CH₃)₃)^m, 63.9 (NCH₂)^m, 63.9 (NCH₂)^M,

604 (NC(Ar)₃)^m, 60.0 (NC(Ar)₃)^M, 59.0 (NCH₂)^m, 59.0 (NCH₂)^M, 23.3 (2 x NC(CH₃)₃)^{M+m}. **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₃₉H₃₉N₃O₂ + Na⁺ : 636.2661 [M+Na]⁺; found 636.2642. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max}= 3057, 2960, 2924, 2854, 1489, 1292, 1168, 1030, 698.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-*N*-(naphthalen-1-yl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxamide, **27**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.44 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 1-naphthyl isocyanate **S** (81 mg, 0.07 mL, 0.48 mmol)). Compound **27** was obtained as a white solid (99 mg, 0.24 mmol, 55% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (4:6 EtOAc/hexane). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.85 – 7.81 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.75 – 7.71 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.64 – 7.61 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.49 – 7.35 (m, 8H, Ar-H), 6.23 (bs, 1H, NH), 4.95 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.31 (dd, *J* = 10.4, 1.3 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.17 (dd, *J* = 10.4, 1.3 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.99 (dd, *J* = 9.9, 1.4 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.71 (dd, *J* = 9.9, 1.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.08 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 157.3 (C=O), 137.2 (Ar-C_q), 134.2 (Ar-C_q), 132.8 (Ar-C_q), 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar-C), 128.7 (Ar-C), 127.9 (Ar-C_q), 127.5 (2 x Ar-C), 126.4 (Ar-C), 126.1 (Ar-C), 125.8 (Ar-C), 125.5 (Ar-C), 121.0 (Ar-C), 121.0 (Ar-C), 80.7 (spiro-C_q), 68.3 (NCH), 62.7 (NCH₂), 59.4 (NCH₂), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₅H₂₇N₃O₂ + Na⁺: 424.2001 [M+Na]⁺; found 424.2007. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max}= 3256, 3051, 2971, 2867, 1736, 1648, 1532, 1501, 1362, 1272, 791, 769.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxamide, **28**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-chlorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.41 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 2,4-dichlorophenyl isocyanate **T** (85 mg, 0.45 mmol)). Compound **28** was obtained as a white solid (0.12 g, 0.26 mmol, 63% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-chlorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after washing the crude with hexane/diethyl ether (3 x 10 mL, 4:1 v/v). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.10 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.46 (d, *J* = 8.4, 2H, Ar-H), 7.41 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.31 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.18 (dd, *J* = 8.9, 2.4 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 6.38 (bs, 1H, NH), 4.95 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.36 (dd, *J* = 10.2, 1.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.22 (dd, *J* = 10.2, 1.3 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.07 (dd, *J* = 9.8, 1.3 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.78 (dd, *J* = 9.8, 1.2 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.08 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.0 (C=O), 135.5 (Ar-C_q), 134.8 (Ar-C_q), 133.9 (Ar-C_q), 129.4 (2 x Ar-C), 128.9 (2 x Ar-C), 128.6 (Ar-C), 128.0 (Ar-C), 127.9 (Ar-C_q), 122.5 (Ar-C_q), 121.2 (Ar-C), 80.3 (spiro-C_q), 67.5 (NCH), 62.3 (NCH₂), 59.3 (NCH₂), 58.9 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₁H₂₂Cl₃N₃O₂ + Na⁺: 477.0675 [M+Na]⁺; found 477.0708. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max}= 3290, 2969, 1667, 1510, 1362, 1293, 1090, 861, 820, 745, 607.

***N*-(3,5-Bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxamide, 29**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **3** (0.45 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl isothiocyanate **U** (0.13 g, 0.50 mmol)). Compound **29** was obtained as a white solid (0.14 g, 0.28 mmol, 62% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (1:4 EtOAc/hexane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.91 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 7.61 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.49 (dd, $J = 8.0, 5.5$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.13 (t, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 4.97 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.49 (d, $J = 11.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.38 (d, $J = 11.8$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.15 (d, $J = 10.7$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.68

(d, $J = 10.7$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.08 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 179.2 (C=S), 163.0 (d, $^1J = 248.3$ Hz, Ar- FC_q), 139.9 (2 x Ar- C_q), 132.0 (q, $^2J = 33.7$ Hz, 2 x CCF_3), 129.4 (d, $^3J = 8.2$ Hz, 2 x Ar-FC), 123.0 (q, $^1J = 272.9$ Hz, 2 x CF_3), 123.6 (q, $^5J = 2.8$ Hz, 2 x Ar- CCF_3), 118.8 (q, $^3J = 11.3$ Hz, 2 x Ar- CCF_3), 116.2 (d, $^2J = 21.6$ Hz, 2 x Ar-FC), 79.4 (spiro- C_q), 67.2 (NCH), 65.2 (bs, NCH_2), 61.0 (bs, NCH_2), 59.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -63.01 (s, 6F), -112.37 – -112.44 (m, 1F). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{F}_7\text{N}_3\text{OS} + \text{Na}^+$: 544.1270 [$M + \text{Na}$] $^+$; found 544.1286. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2973, 1548, 1474, 1373, 1276, 1177, 1131, 1100, 886, 844$.

(4-Bromophenyl)(2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-yl)methanone, 30

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.88 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 4-bromobenzoyl chloride **P** (213 mg, 0.97 mmol)). Compound **30** was obtained as a colourless oil (0.23 g, 0.56 mmol, 63% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (1:4 EtOAc/hexane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.52 – 7.33 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 4.96 – 4.91 (bs, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.51 – 4.41 (bs, 1H, NCHH), 4.36 (dd, $J = 11.6, 1.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.24 – 4.21 (bs, 1H, NCHH), 3.97 – 3.90 (bs, 1H, NCHH), 1.07 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 169.3 (C=O), 137.0 (Ar- C_q), 136.8 (Ar- C_q), 131.7 (Ar-C), 129.5 (2 x Ar-C), 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar- C_q), 127.4 (2 x Ar-C), 125.9 (2 x Ar-C), 81.7 (spiro- C_q), 68.1 (NCH), 62.7 (NCH_2), 62.0 (NCH_2), 59.2 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.2 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{Na}^+$: 437.0841 [$M + \text{Na}$] $^+$; found 437.0832. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2969, 2929, 2866, 1636, 1589, 1415, 1207, 1069, 1011, 700$.

4-(2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carbonyl)benzonitrile, 31

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.45 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 4-cyanobenzoyl chloride **Q** (83 mg, 0.50 mmol)). Compound **31** was obtained as a white waxy solid (94 mg, 0.26 mmol, 58% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column

chromatography on silica gel (3:7 EtOAc/hexane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.68 – 7.61 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.54 – 7.52 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.46 – 7.35 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 4.98 – 4.91 (bs, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.53 – 4.44 (bs, 1H, NCHH), 4.37 (d, $J = 12.3$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.23 (d, $J = 9.7$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.89 (d, $J = 10.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.08 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 168.1 (C=O), 136.9 (Ar-C_q), 136.6 (Ar-C_q), 132.4 (2 x Ar-C), 129.2 (4 x Ar-C), 129.5 (2 x Ar-C), 127.6 (Ar-C), 127.4 (Ar-C_q), 118.1 (CN), 114.9 (Ar-C_q), 81.1 (spiro-C_q), 68.1 (NCH), 62.6 (NCH₂), 62.1 (NCH₂), 59.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2 + \text{Na}^+$: 384.1688 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 384.1716. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2929, 2231, 1633, 1428, 1206, 906, 725, 699, 646$.

1-(2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-yl)-2-(4-isobutylphenyl)propan-1-one, **32**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.45 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 2-(4-isobutylphenyl)propanoyl chloride **V** (0.11 g, 0.50 mmol)). Compound **32** was obtained as mixture of diastereomers (*dr* ca 6:4) and rotamers. The diastereomers were separated by flash column chromatography (3:7 EtOAc/hexane) as white solids (major: 84 mg, 0.19 mmol; minor: 56 mg, 0.14 mmol; 74% combined yield based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps

GP6 and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel. **Major**: $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 7.55 – 7.12 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 5.19 – 4.96 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.49 – 3.60 (m, 4H, NCH₂), 3.69 – 3.60 (m, 1H, COCH), 2.52 – 2.44 (m, 2H, Ar-CH₂), 1.93 – 1.80 (m, 1H, Ar-CH₂CH), 1.33 – 1.23 (m, 3H, CHCH₃), 1.06 – 1.04 (m, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 0.95 – 0.89 (m, 6H, 2 x CH₃) $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 176.1 (C=O), 175.9 (C=O), 141.8 (Ar-C_q), 141.8 (Ar-C_q), 139.5 (Ar-C_q), 139.1 (Ar-C_q), 138.5 (Ar-C_q), 138.3 (Ar-C_q), 130.6 (Ar-C), 130.6 (Ar-C), 130.0 (Ar-C), 129.9 (Ar-C), 129.7 (Ar-C), 129.6 (Ar-C), 128.7 (Ar-C), 128.3 (Ar-C), 128.2 (Ar-C), 128.2 (Ar-C), 81.9 (spiro-C_q), 81.5 (spiro-C_q), 68.9 (NCH), 68.8 (NCH), 64.2 (NCH₂), 61.9 (NCH₂), 61.0 (NCH₂), 60.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 60.2 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.7 (NCH₂), 46.0 (2 x Ar-CH₂), 43.3 (2 x COCH), 31.5 (ArCH₂CH), 31.4 ((ArCH₂CH), 23.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 22.7 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 19.3 (CHCH₃), 19.1 (CHCH₃). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{H}^+$: 421.2777 [$M+\text{H}$]⁺; found 421.2825. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2954, 2922, 2852, 1730, 1654, 1455, 1363, 1062, 700$. **Minor**: $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 7.55 – 6.89 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 5.15 – 5.10 (m, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.56 – 3.68 (m, 4H, NCH₂), 3.96 – 3.57 (m, 1H, COCH), 2.49 – 2.41 (m, 2H, Ar-CH₂), 1.90 – 1.77 (m, 1H, Ar-CH₂CH), 1.33 – 1.27 (m, 3H, CHCH₃), 1.07 – 1.04 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 0.92 – 0.91 (m, 6H, 2 x CH₃) $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 176.0 (C=O), 175.9 (C=O), 141.8 (Ar-C_q), 141.4 (Ar-C_q), 130.6 (Ar-C_q), 130.4 (Ar-C_q), 129.9 (Ar-C_q), 129.9 (Ar-C_q), 129.8 (Ar-C), 129.7 (Ar-C), 129.3 (Ar-C), 128.8 (Ar-C), 128.2 (Ar-C), 128.2 (Ar-C), 127.8 (Ar-C), 81.8 (2 x spiro-C_q), 68.7 (NCH), 68.6 (NCH), 62.0 (NCH₂), 60.8 (NCH₂), 59.4 (NCH₂), 60.2 (2 x $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 58.6 (NCH₂), 46.1 (Ar-CH₂), 46.0 (Ar-CH₂), 43.4 (COCH), 43.1 (COCH), 31.4 (ArCH₂CH), 31.4 (ArCH₂CH), 23.6 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 23.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 21.4 (CHCH₃), 21.4 (CHCH₃), 22.8 (CHCH₃), 22.8 (CHCH₃), 19.2 (CHCH₃), 19.1 (CHCH₃). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{H}^+$: 421.2777 [$M+\text{H}$]⁺; found 421.2825. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2956, 2926, 1726, 1651, 1435, 1363, 1219, 890, 700$.

Note: Doubling of ^1H - and ^{13}C -NMR signals observed due to the presence of rotamers.

1-(2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-yl)-2-(2-fluoro-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)propan-1-one, 33

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.88 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: flurbiprofen acid chloride **Y** (0.25 g, 0.97 mmol)). Compound **33** was obtained as mixture of diastereomers and rotamers as a white solid (0.16 g, 0.36 mmol, 41% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**, *dr* ca. 1:1) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (2:1 Hexane/EtOAc). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 7.51 – 6.80 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 4.92 – 4.75 (m, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.25 – 3.71 (m, 4H, NCH_2), 3.58 –

3.29 (m, 1H, CHCH_3), 1.39 – 1.25 (m, 3H, CHCH_3), 1.02 – 1.01 (m, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.9 (C=O), 172.9 (2 x C=O), 172.5 (C=O), 159.9 (d, $^1J_{\text{CF}} = 248.6$ Hz, Ar-C_q), 159.8 (d, $^1J_{\text{CF}} = 248.8$ Hz, 2 x Ar-C_q), 159.6 (d, $^1J_{\text{CF}} = 248.7$ Hz, Ar-C_q), 142.6 (Ar-C_q), 142.5 (Ar-C_q), 142.1 (Ar-C_q), 142.0 (Ar-C_q), 137.1 (2 x Ar-C_q), 136.8 (2 x Ar-C_q), 136.7 (Ar-C_q), 135.6 (2 x Ar-C_q), 135.5 (Ar-C_q), 131.2 (d, $^3J_{\text{CF}} = 4.0$ Hz, Ar-C), 131.0 (d, $^3J_{\text{CF}} = 3.7$ Hz, Ar-C), 130.8 (d, $^3J_{\text{CF}} = 3.9$ Hz, Ar-C), 129.1, 129.1, 129.0, 129.0, 128.8, 128.8, 128.6, 128.5, 128.5, 128.4, 127.9, 127.8, 127.7, 127.7, 127.6, 127.5, 127.4, 127.2, 126.8, 123.5 (d, $^4J_{\text{CF}} = 3.3$ Hz, Ar-C), 123.4 (d, $^4J_{\text{CF}} = 3.2$ Hz, Ar-C), 123.3 (d, $^4J_{\text{CF}} = 3.2$ Hz, Ar-C), 115.2 (d, $^2J_{\text{CF}} = 23.5$ Hz, Ar-C), 115.1 (d, $^2J_{\text{CF}} = 26.1$ Hz, Ar-C), 115.1 (d, $^2J_{\text{CF}} = 23.1$ Hz, Ar-C), 114.9 (d, $^2J_{\text{CF}} = 22.8$ Hz, Ar-C), 80.5 (spiro-C_q), 80.4 (spiro-C_q), 68.3 (NCH), 68.2 (NCH), 68.1 (NCH), 68.0 (NCH), 63.3 (NCH₂), 63.2 (NCH₂), 61.4 (NCH₂), 61.2 (NCH₂), 59.7 (NCH₂), 59.6 (NCH₂), 59.2 (NCH₂), 59.2 (NCH₂), 52.5 (4 x $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 42.4 (COCH), 42.2 (2 x COCH), 42.0 (COCH), 23.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 19.3 (CHCH_3), 19.2 (CHCH_3), 18.9 (CHCH_3). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CD_3OD) δ -118.73 – -118.88 (m, 4 x F). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{31}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{Na}^+$: 481.2267 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 481.2262. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3032, 2970, 2920, 1647, 1433, 1362, 1218, 1129, 886, 831$.

Note: Doubling of ^1H - and ^{13}C -NMR signals observed due to the presence of rotamers.

1-(2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-yl)-2-(1-(4-chlorobenzoyl)-5-methoxy-2-methyl-3a,7a-dihydro-1*H*-indol-3-yl)ethan-1-one, 34

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.44 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: 1-(4-chlorobenzoyl)-5-methoxy-2-methyl-1*H*-indole-3-acetyl chloride **X** (0.18 g, 0.48 mmol)). Compound **34** was obtained as a yellow oil as a mixture of diastereomers (0.15 g, 0.26 mmol, 59% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (5:95 MeOH/DCM). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.68 – 7.31 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 6.84 – 6.61 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 4.94 – 4.86 (m, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.29 – 4.00 (m, 4H, NCH_2), 3.79 – 3.78 (m, 3H, OCH_3), 3.51 – 3.35 (m, 2H, COCH_2), 2.37 –

2.19 (s, 3H, NCCH_3), 1.07 – 1.05 (m, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.0 (C=O), 168.3 (C=O), 156.2 (C=O), 156.2 (C=O), 139.5 (Ar-C_q), 139.3 (Ar-C_q), 137.0 (Ar-C_q), 136.7 (Ar-C_q), 135.5 (Ar-C_q), 135.5 (Ar-C_q), 134.0 (Ar-C_q), 134.0 (Ar-C_q), 131.3 (2 x Ar-C), 131.3 (2 x Ar-C),

130.8 (Ar-C_q), 130.6 (Ar-C_q), 129.3 (2 x Ar-C), 129.2 (2 x Ar-C), 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 128.9 (Ar-C), 128.7 (Ar-C), 127.5 (Ar-C), 127.2 (Ar-C), 115.1 (2 x Ar-C), 112.5 (Ar-C), 112.0 (Ar-C), 101.4 (Ar-C), 101.2 (Ar-C), 80.5 (2 x spiro-C_q), 68.2 (NCH), 68.1 (NCH), 63.5 (NCH₂), 61.5 (NCH₂), 60.1 (NCH₂), 59.3 (NC(CH₃)₃), 59.2 (NCH₂), 58.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.8 (2 x OCH₃), 29.2 (COCH₂), 28.2 (COCH₂), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃), 13.6 (NCCH₃), 13.4 (NCCH₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₃₃H₃₆ClN₃O₄+Na⁺: 596.2136 [M+Na]⁺; found 596.2144. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 2970, 2930 1679, 1590, 1476, 1363, 1324, 1222, 910, 731.

Note: Doubling of ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR signals observed due to the presence of rotamers.

2-(2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-yl)-1-(6-methoxynaphthalen-2-yl)propan-1-one, 35

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP7** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **3** (0.89 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP7**: naproxenoyl chloride **W** (0.24 g, 0.98 mmol)). Compound **35** was obtained as mixture of diastereomers and rotamers as a colourless film (0.23 g, 0.50 mmol, 56% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP7**, *dr* ca. 1:1) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (4:6 EtOAc/hexane). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ 7.81 – 6.65 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 5.20 – 5.07 (m, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.67 – 3.96 (m, 3H, NCH₂), 3.89 – 3.86 (m, 3H, OCH₃), 3.87 – 3.86 (m, 9H, 3 x OCH₃), 3.80 – 3.71 (m, 1H, NCH₂), 3.68 – 3.48 (m, 1H, COCH), 1.36 – 1.20

(m, 3H, CHCH₃), 0.95 – 0.94 (m, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO) δ 173.4 (C=O), 173.3 (C=O), 173.3 (C=O), 173.1 (C=O), 163.6, 163.5, 163.0, 162.2, 161.0, 160.6, 157.6, 157.6, 157.6, 136.9, 136.8, 136.6, 136.5, 134.4, 134.3, 133.9, 133.9, 133.7, 133.7, 133.6, 133.6, 130.3, 130.2, 130.1, 130.0, 129.9, 129.8, 129.6, 129.6, 129.4, 129.1, 129.0, 129.0, 128.9, 128.9, 128.8, 127.5, 127.5, 127.4, 126.7, 126.7, 126.6, 126.3, 126.0, 126.0, 125.8, 125.5, 119.2, 119.2, 119.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116.0, 115.9, 115.9, 115.8, 115.5, 115.5, 106.2, 106.2, 106.2, 80.4 (spiro-C_q), 80.4 (spiro-C_q), 80.2 (spiro-C_q), 80.1 (spiro-C_q), 65.3 (NCH), 65.2 (NCH), 65.1 (2 x NCH), 62.6 (NCH₂), 62.4 (NCH₂), 60.6 (NCH₂), 60.4 (NCH₂), 59.3 (NCH₂), 58.8 (NCH₂), 58.7 (2 x NCH₂), 58.7 (2 x NCH₂), 58.6 (2 x NCH₂), 58.6 (2 x NCH₂), 57.1 (NCH₂), 57.0 (NCH₂), 55.2 (4 x OCH₃), 41.1 (CHCH₃), 41.1 (CHCH₃), 41.0 (CHCH₃), 40.8 (CHCH₃), 22.9 (4 x NC(CH₃)₃), 19.1 (CHCH₃), 18.9 (CHCH₃), 18.9 (CHCH₃), 18.7 (CHCH₃). ¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, DMSO) δ -113.83 – -114.05 (m, 4 x F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₈H₃₁FN₂O₃ + Na⁺: 485.2216 [M+Na]⁺; found 485.2216. **IR** (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 2965, 2926, 2854, 1646, 1604 1507 1436, 1388, 1352, 1264, 1214, 1155.

Note: Doubling of ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR signals observed due to the presence of rotamers.

4-(2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-yl)benzotrile, 36

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP8** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.50 mmol) (Aryl bromide for **GP8**: 4-bromobenzotrile **AA** (89 mg, 0.50 mmol)). Compound **36** was obtained as a white solid (95 mg, 0.28 mmol, 57% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP8**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (1:4 EtOAc/hexane). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.51 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.44 – 7.33 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 6.28 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz,

2H, Ar-H), 5.03 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.21 – 4.15 (m, 2H, NCH₂), 3.87 (d, *J* = 9.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.71 (dd, *J* = 9.7, 1.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.11 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 152.6 (N-C_q), 137.3 (Ar-C_q), 133.4 (2 x Ar-C), 129.0 (2 x Ar-C), 128.6 (Ar-C), 127.5 (2 x Ar-C), 120.4 (CN), 111.5 (2 x Ar-C), 99.4 (Ar-C_q), 81.3 (spiro-C_q), 68.2 (NCH), 64.6 (NCH₂), 60.7 (NCH₂), 59.2 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₁H₂₃N₃O + Na⁺: 356.1739 [M+Na]⁺; found 356.1735. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** ν_{max} = 2974, 2927, 2848, 2211, 1601, 1517, 1457, 1384.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-phenyl-6-(2-(trifluoromethyl)pyrimidin-5-yl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane, **37**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP8** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine **1** (0.50 mmol) (Aryl bromide for **GP8**: 5-bromo-2-(trifluoromethyl)pyrimidine **AB** (0.11 g, 0.50 mmol)). Compound **37** was obtained as a yellow oil (52 mg, 0.14 mmol, 28% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(phenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP8**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (15:85 EtOAc/hexane).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.88 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 7.53 – 7.51 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.46 – 7.42 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.40 – 7.36 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 5.05 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.32 – 4.27 (m, 2H, NCH₂), 3.99 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.83 (d, *J* = 9.7, 1H, NCHH), 1.11 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 145.9 (CCF₃), 144.1 (Ar-C_q), 139.9 (2 x Ar-C), 136.9 (N-C_q), 129.2 (2 x Ar-C), 128.9 (Ar-C), 127.5 (2 x Ar-C), 120.2 (q, ¹*J* = 273.5 Hz, CF₃), 82.1 (spiro-C_q), 68.3 (NCH), 65.1 (NCH₂), 61.4 (NCH₂), 59.3 (NC(CH₃)₃), 23.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). **¹⁹F NMR** (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -68.97 (s, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₉H₂₁F₃N₄O + Na⁺: 401.1565 [M+Na]⁺; found 401.1559. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** ν_{max} = 2968, 2925, 2853, 1572, 1377, 1216, 1182, 1134, 1111, 891, 699, 639.

2-(*tert*-Butyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-(1-methyl-1*H*-indol-5-yl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane, **38**

Prepared following **GP6** and **GP8** consecutively from *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-methoxyphenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine (0.92 mmol) (Electrophile for **GP8**: 5-bromo-1-methylindole **AC** (0.19 g, 0.92 mmol)). Compound **38** was obtained as a brown solid (0.19 g, 0.49 mmol, 53% based on *N*-((1-azabicyclo[1.1.0]butan-3-yl)(4-methoxyphenyl)methyl)-*N*-(*tert*-butyl)hydroxylamine over two steps **GP6** and **GP8**) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (15:85 EtOAc/hexane). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.47 (t, *J* = 10.4 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.10 (t, *J* = 16.0 Hz, 1H Ar-H), 6.95 – 6.93 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 6.43 (dd, *J* = 8.7, 2.2 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 6.28 (d, *J* = 3.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 4.99 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 4.11 (d, *J*

= 8.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 4.06 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.83 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.74 (d, *J* = 3.9 Hz, 2H, NCH₂), 3.71 (s, 3H, NCH₃), 1.12 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 159.6 (COCH₃), 145.8 (NAr-C_q), 131.6 (Ar-C_q), 130.2 (Ar-C_q), 129.3 (NCHC=), 129.1 Ar-C_q, 128.9 (2 x Ar-C), 114.1 (2 x Ar-C), 109.6 (Ar-C), 109.4 (Ar-C), 102.8 (Ar-C), 99.8 (NCHC=C), 81.8 (spiro-C_q), 68.0 (NCH), 66.2 (NCH₂), 61.9 (NCH₂), 59.0 (NC(CH₃)₃), 55.4 (OCH₃), 33.0 (NCH₃), 23.5 (NC(CH₃)₃). **HRMS** (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₄H₂₉N₃O₂ + Na⁺: 414.2157 [M+Na]⁺; found 414.2162. **IR (film, cm⁻¹):** ν_{max} = 2926, 2835, 1611, 1493, 1421, 1277, 1243, 1170, 1033, 835.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(phenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidone-1-carboxylate, 39**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **5** (93 mg, 0.28 mmol). Compound **39** was obtained white solid (82 mg, 0.24 mmol, 85%) without further purification. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36 – 7.27 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 3.93 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.85 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.82 (s, 1H, NHCH), 3.72 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.59 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.35 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.03 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.3 (C=O), 138.1 (Ar-C_q), 128.9 (2 x Ar-C), 127.8 (Ar-C), 127.6 (2 x Ar-C), 79.5 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 71.6 (C_q-OH), 62.2 (NCH), 61.4 (bs, NCH₂), 52.9 (bs, NCH₂), 51.5

($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 30.3 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 357.2154 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 357.2154. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 2970, 2927, 1827, 1699, 1455, 1391, 1157, 768, 702$.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(4-methoxyphenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidone-1-carboxylate, 40**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **15** (76 mg, 0.21 mmol). Compound **40** was obtained as yellow oil (47 mg, 0.13 mmol, 62%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (6:4 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 7.38 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 6.89 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H) 3.96 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 2H, NCH₂), 3.85 (br, 1H, NHCH), 3.79 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 3.72 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.47 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.39 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 0.99 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 160.4 (Ar-C_q), 158.1 (C=O) 135.0 (Ar-C_q), 130.6 (2 x Ar-C), 114.4 (2 x Ar-C),

80.9 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 79.3 (C_q-OH), 73.5 (2 x NCH₂), 62.9 (NCH), 55.6 (CH₃), 52.0 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 30.5 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.6 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4 + \text{Na}^+$: 387.2260 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 387.2245. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3359, 2960, 2926, 1677, 1511, 1248, 1162, 1035, 771$.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(4-chlorophenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidone-1-carboxylate, 41**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **6** (95 mg, 0.26 mmol). Compound **41** was obtained as white solid (49.2 mg, 0.133 mmol, 50%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.4$ (3:2 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32 – 7.27 (d, $J = 4.2$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H overlapping d, 2H, Ar-H), 3.90 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.85 – 3.82 (m, 1H, NHCH overlapping 1H, NCHH), 3.69 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.58 (d, $J = 9.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.37 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.02 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.1 (C=O), 140.2 (Ar-C_q), 133.7 (Ar-C_q), 129.0 (2 x Ar-C), 129.0 (2 x Ar-C), 79.7 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 71.7 (C_q-OH), 71.1 (bs, NCH₂), 61.6 (NCH), 61.3 (bs, NCH₂), 51.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 30.4 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$).

HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{27}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 391.1764 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺; found 391.1750. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3340, 2964, 2930, 1680, 1413, 1365, 1258, 1159, 1091, 808, 730$.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(4-fluorophenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidone-1-carboxylate, 42**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **8** (168 mg, 0.48 mmol). Compound **42** was obtained as colourless oil (59 mg, 0.16 mmol, 33%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (1:99 MeOH/DCM). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 7.49 (dd, $J = 8.7, 5.5$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.04 (dd, $J = 8.7, 5.5$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 3.98 (dd, $J = 9.3, 0.7$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.93 (dd, 1H, $J = 9.3, 0.7$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.90 (s, 1H, NHCH), 3.73 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.46 (d, 1H, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 1H, NCHH) 1.40 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 0.98 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 163.5 (d, $^1J = 243.9$ Hz, Ar- C_q), 158.2 (C=O), 139.4 (d, $^4J = 3.2$ Hz, Ar- C_q), 131.4 (d, $^3J = 7.9$ Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 115.5 (d, $^2J = 21.3$ Hz, 2x Ar-C), 80.9 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 73.5 ($\text{C}_q\text{-OH}$), 73.4 (2 x NCH $_2$), 62.7 (NCH), 51.9 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 30.6 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.6 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CD_3OD) δ -117.88 – -118.05 (m, F). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{29}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 375.2060 [$M + \text{Na}$] $^+$; found 375.2065. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3352, 2966, 2492, 1673, 1508, 1417, 1221, 1158, 977$.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidone-1-carboxylate, 43**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **10** (116 mg, 0.29 mmol). Compound **43** was obtained as white solid (40.8 mg, 0.101 mmol, 35%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.4$ (3:2 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.60 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.49 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 3.94 – 3.92 (m, 1H, NHCH overlapping 1H, NCHH), 3.85 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.68 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.59 (d, $J = 9.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.36 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.02 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.3 (C=O), 145.7 (s, Ar- C_q), 130.2 (q, $^2J = 32.2$ Hz, Ar- C_q), 128.1 (s, 2 x Ar-C), 125.7 (q, $^3J = 7.5$ Hz, 2 x Ar-C), 124.1 (q, $^1J = 271.7$ Hz, CF_3), 79.7 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 71.7 ($\text{C}_q\text{-OH}$), 61.9 (NCH), 61.4 (bs, 2 x NCH $_2$), 51.6 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 30.4 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.5 (s, F). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 425.2028 [$M + \text{Na}$] $^+$; found 425.2031. IR (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3362, 2964, 2927, 2158, 1676, 1417, 1324, 1123, 1066, 771$.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(4-heptanoylphenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidone-1-carboxylate, 44**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-Butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(4-heptanoylphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **13** (0.12 g, 0.28 mmol). Compound **44** was obtained as a colourless oil (0.68 g, 0.15 mmol, 54%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (2:98 MeOH/DCM). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.93 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H, 2 x Ar-H), 7.46 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, 2 x Ar-H), 3.94 – 3.92 (m, 1H, NCHH overlapping 1H, NHCH), 3.86 (d, $J = 9.3$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.71 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.59 (d, $J = 9.6$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 2.94 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2H, COCH_2), 1.76 – 1.68 (m, 2H, COCH_2CH_2), 1.35 – 1.30 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ overlapping m, 6H, 3 x CH $_2$), 1.03 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 0.89 (t, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 3H). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 200.2 ($\text{CH}_2\text{C=O}$), 156.3 (C=O), 146.4 (Ar- C_q), 136.7 (Ar- C_q), 128.6 (2 x Ar-C), 128.0 (2 x Ar-C), 79.7 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 71.6 ($\text{C}_q\text{-OH}$), 62.1 (NCH), 61.3 (bs, NCH $_2$), 52.0 (bs, NCH $_2$), 38.8 ($\text{CH}_2\text{C=O}$), 31.8 (CH $_2$), 30.3 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 29.2 (CH $_2$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 24.4 (CH $_2$), 22.7 (CH $_2$), 14.2 (CH $_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for

$C_{26}H_{42}N_2O_3+Na^+$: 469.3042 $[M+Na]^+$; found 469.3066. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 3351, 2959, 2929, 1680, 1605, 1412, 1355, 1162, 771.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(pyridin-3-yl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidine-1-carboxylate, 45**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **14** (0.18 g, 0.53 mmol). Compound **45** was obtained as white solid (35 mg, 0.10 mmol, 19%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (5:95 MeOH/DCM). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 8.59 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 8.46 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.75 – 7.72 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.25 – 7.23 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 3.94 (d, J = 9.3, 1H, NCHH), 3.89 (s, 1H, NHCH), 3.84 (d, 1H, J = 9.3, 1H, NCHH), 3.69 (d, J = 9.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.48 (s, 1H, OH), 1.47 (s, 1H, NH), 1.37 (s, 9H, $OC(CH_3)_3$), 1.00 (s, 9H, $NC(CH_3)_3$). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (101

MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 156.4 (C=O), 149.5 (Ar-C), 148.9 (Ar-C), 137.4 (Ar-C), 135.4 (Ar-C_q), 123.6 (Ar-C), 79.8 ($OC(CH_3)_3$), 71.9 (C_q-OH), 70.4 (bs, NCH₂), 61.3 (bs, NCH₂), 60.1 (NCH), 51.5 ($NC(CH_3)_3$), 30.4 ($OC(CH_3)_3$), 28.4 ($NC(CH_3)_3$). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $C_{18}H_{29}N_3O_3+Na^+$: 358.2107 $[M+Na]^+$; found 358.2100. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 3337, 3167, 2966, 2928, 1826, 1694, 1476, 1300, 1154, 1071, 770, 732.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(2-fluorophenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidine-1-carboxylate, 46**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(2-fluorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **9** (0.27 g, 0.76 mmol). Compound **46** was obtained as white solid (0.169 g, 0.481 mmol, 63%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel R_f = 0.3 (3:2 hexane/AcOEt). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.38 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.29 – 7.24 (m, 1H, Ar-H), 7.15 (td, J = 7.5, 1.1 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.07 (td, J = 7.5, 1.1 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 4.20 (bs, 1H, NCHH), 3.92 – 3.85 (m, 1H, NCHH overlapping 1H, NHCH), 3.79 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.62 (d, J = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.35 (s, 9H, $OC(CH_3)_3$), 1.02 (s, 9H, $NC(CH_3)_3$). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 160.3 (d,

1J = 243.8 Hz, CF), 156.3 (C=O), 129.3 (d, 3J = 8.6 Hz, Ar-C), 129.4 – 128.5 (m, Ar-C overlapping Ar-C_q), 124.7 (d, 4J = 3.4 Hz, Ar-C), 115.9 (d, 2J = 23.4 Hz, Ar-C), 79.4 ($OC(CH_3)_3$), 71.9 (C_q-OH), 60.6 (bs, NCH₂), 55.0 (bs, NCH₂), 51.4 ($NC(CH_3)_3$), 30.1 ($OC(CH_3)_3$), 28.5 ($NC(CH_3)_3$). ^{19}F NMR (376.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ -116.7 (s, F). HRMS (ESI+) m/z calcd for $C_{19}H_{29}FN_2O_3+Na^+$: 375.2060 $[M+Na]^+$; found 375.2065. IR (film, cm^{-1}): ν_{max} = 3366, 2966, 1672, 1453, 1365, 1215, 1157, 1071, 858, 755.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidine-1-carboxylate, 47**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **11** (0.16 g, 0.41 mmol). Compound **47** was obtained as yellow oil (139 mg, 0.34 mmol, 83%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (3:2 hexane/AcOEt). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.68 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.59 – 7.52 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.39 (t, J = 7.5 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 4.45 (bs, 1H, NCHH), 3.92 – 3.87 (m, 1H, NHCH), 3.81 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.52 (d, J = 9.7 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.48 (d, 1H, J = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH) 1.37 (s, 9H,

$OC(CH_3)_3$), 1.07 (s, 9H, $NC(CH_3)_3$). $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR (101 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 156.4 (C=O), 141.7 (Ar-C_q), 132.9 (Ar-C), 127.8 (2 x Ar-C), 127.7 (q, 2J = 23.9 Hz, Ar-C_q), 126.1 (d, 4J = 5.9 Hz, Ar-C), 123.1 (q, 1J = 276.4 Hz, Ar-C), 79.5 ($OC(CH_3)_3$), 71.2 (C_q-OH), 63.5 (bs, NCH₂), 59.1 (bs, NCH₂), 56.6 (NCH), 51.6 ($NC(CH_3)_3$), 30.0 ($OC(CH_3)_3$), 28.5

(NC(CH₃)₃). ¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -57.06 (s, F). HRMS (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₀H₂₉F₃N₂O₃ +Na⁺: 425.2028 [M+Na]⁺; found 425.2032. IR (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3384, 2971, 1829, 1678, 1306, 1157, 1119, 769.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidide-1-carboxylate, 48**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **16** (0.11 g, 0.28 mmol). Compound **48** was obtained as a colourless oil (0.3 g, 0.08 mmol, 28%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (2:98 MeOH/DCM). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.16 – 7.10 (bs, 1H, Ar-H), 7.04 (t, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 6.94 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 1.4 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 3.99 (dd, *J* = 9.1, 3.3 Hz, 2H, NCH₂), 3.95 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.87 (s, 3H, OCH₃ overlapping 1H, NHCH), 3.72 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.46 (d, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.40 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.01 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 158.4 (C=O), 153.7 (Ar-C_q), 147.8 (Ar-C_q), 136.6 (Ar-C_q), 124.6 (2 x Ar-C), 121.4 (Ar-C), 112.7 (Ar-C), 80.8, 73.8 (2 x NCH₂), 60.9 (NCH), 56.2 (2 x CH₃), 51.9 (NC(CH₃)₃), 30.5 (OC(CH₃)₃), 28.6 (NC(CH₃)₃). HRMS (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₁H₃₄N₂O₅ +Na⁺: 417.2365 [M+Na]⁺; found 417.2361. IR (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3411, 2964, 2927, 1698, 1475, 1261, 1161, 1062, 1007, 770, 750.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidide-1-carboxylate, 49**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **17** (0.10 g, 0.24 mmol). Compound **49** was obtained as colourless film (37 mg, 0.087 mmol, 36%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel (2.5:97.5 MeOH/DCM). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.53 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 3.95 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.86 (s, 6H, 2 x OCH₃), 3.84 – 3.83 (m, 1H, NHCH overlapping 3H, OCH₃), 3.81 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.72 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.64 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.39 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.06 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.4 (C=O), 153.5 (2 x Ar-C_q), 137.6 (Ar-C_q), 132.9 (Ar-C_q), 104.5 (2 x Ar-C), 79.6 (OC(CH₃)₃), 71.6 (C_q-OH), 62.4 (NCH), 62.0 (bs, NCH₂), 61.0 (OCH₃), 59.3 (bs, NCH₂), 56.4 (2 x OCH₃), 51.4 (NC(CH₃)₃), 30.2 (OC(CH₃)₃), 28.5 (NC(CH₃)₃). HRMS (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₂₂H₃₆N₂O₆+Na⁺: 447.2471 [M+Na]⁺; found 447.2457. IR (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3352, 2959, 1697, 1590, 1419, 1126, 859, 770.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((*tert*-butylamino)(3-chlorophenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidide-1-carboxylate, 50**

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert*-butyl 2-(*tert*-butyl)-3-(3-chlorophenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate **7** (82 mg, 0.22 mmol). Compound **50** was obtained as white solid (44.1 mg, 0.119 mmol, 53%) solid after flash column chromatography on silica gel *R_f* = 0.3 (3:2 hexane/AcOEt). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40 (bs, 1H, Ar-H), 7.32 – 7.26 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 3.97 (d, 1H, NCHH), 3.89 – 3.87 (m, 1H, NHCH overlapping 1H, NCHH), 3.75 (d, *J* = 9.5 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.64 (d, *J* = 9.6 Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.42 (s, 9H, OC(CH₃)₃), 1.07 (s, 9H, NC(CH₃)₃). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.3 (C=O), 143.9 (Ar-C_q), 134.6 (Ar-C_q), 130.0 (Ar-C), 128.0 (Ar-C), 127.8 (Ar-C), 125.9 (Ar-C), 79.6 (OC(CH₃)₃), 71.7 (C_q-OH), 61.8 (NCH), 61.4 (bs, NCH₂), 59.0 (bs, NCH₂), 51.5 (NC(CH₃)₃), 30.4 (OC(CH₃)₃), 28.4 (NC(CH₃)₃). HRMS (ESI+) *m/z* calcd for C₁₉H₂₇ClN₂O₃ +Na⁺: 391.1764 [M+Na]⁺; found 391.1751. IR (film, cm⁻¹): ν_{max} = 3363, 2967, 1828, 1672, 1419, 1365, 1157, 1075, 771, 694.

tert-Butyl 3-((tert-butylamino)(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methyl)-3-hydroxyazetidide-1-carboxylate, 51

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert-butyl 2-(tert-butyl)-3-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate*

12 (0.08 g, 0.2 mmol). Compound **51** was obtained as white solid (33 mg, 0.082 mmol, 41%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.3$ (3:2 hexane/AcOEt). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.62 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.55 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.46 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 3.94 – 3.91 (m, 1H, NHCH overlapping 1H, NCHH), 3.89 (d, $J = 9.3$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.67 (d, $J = 9.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 3.58 (d, $J = 9.5$ Hz, 1H, NCHH), 1.36 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.02 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.3 (C=O), 142.8 (s, Ar- C_q), 131.2 (bs, Ar-C), 130.7 (q, $^2J = 32.2$ Hz, Ar-Cq), 129.2 (s, Ar-C), 124.1 (q, $^1J = 273.9$ Hz, CF_3), 124.7 (q, $^3J = 7.5$ Hz, Ar-C), 124.5 (bs, Ar-C), 79.7 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 71.7 ($\text{C}_q\text{-OH}$), 61.9 (NCH), 61.5 (bs, NCH_2), 59.0 (bs, NCH_2), 51.6 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 30.4 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.4 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$).

$^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.5 (s, F). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{29}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 425.2028 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 425.2023. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3363, 2969, 1676, 1427, 1327, 1163, 1126, 1073, 705$.

tert-Butyl (E)-3-(1-(tert-butylamino)-2-methyl-3-phenylallyl)-3-hydroxyazetidide-1-carboxylate, 52

Prepared following **GP10** from *tert-butyl (E)-2-(tert-butyl)-3-(1-phenylprop-1-en-2-yl)-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptane-6-carboxylate* **18** (75 mg, 0.20 mmol). Compound **52** was obtained as white solid (45 mg, 0.12 mmol, 60%) after flash column chromatography on silica gel $R_f = 0.4$ (7:3 hexane/AcOEt).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36 – 7.32 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 7.26 – 7.22 (m, 3H, Ar-H overlapping residual solvent), 6.53 (s, 1H, Ar-CH), 3.97 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 2H, NCH_2), 3.81 (m, 2H, NCH_2), 3.49 (s, 1H, NCH), 1.87 (d, $J = 1.0$ Hz, H, Ar- CHCCH_3), 1.42 (s, 9H, $\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.14 (s, 9H, $\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.6 (C=O), 138.0 (Ar- C_q), 137.3 (C=CH), 129.1 (2 x Ar-C), 128.4 (C=CH), 127.8 (Ar-C), 126.9 (2 x Ar-C), 79.6 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 71.3 ($\text{C}_q\text{-OH}$),

65.7 (NCH), 62.2 (bs, NCH_2), 51.3 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 50.4 (bs, NCH_2), 30.1 ($\text{OC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 28.5 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 15.2 (CH_3). **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}^+$: 397.2467 [$M+\text{Na}$] $^+$; found 397.2450. **IR** (film, cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3382, 2958, 2924, 2854, 1676, 1476, 1421, 1160, 1071, 916, 751, 699$.

3-((tert-Butylamino)(phenyl)methyl)azetidide-3-ol, 53

Prepared according to a previously reported procedure.^[15]

A solution of 2-(tert-butyl)-3-phenyl-1-oxa-2,6-diazaspiro[3.3]heptan-6-ium 2,2,2-trifluoroacetate **20** (0.3 mmol) in MeOH (20 mL, 0.015 M) was injected in an H-Cube[®] Pro (ThalesNano) apparatus (operating at 25°C and 1 bar of hydrogen pressure) equipped with a 10%Pd/C cartridge (CatCarts[®]) using a BlueShadow Pump 10P (KNAUER) with a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. After the complete intake of the reagent solution, MeOH was fluxed at the same flow rate. The outgoing

solution was collected for 45 minutes. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to obtain the crude product. $^1\text{H NMR}$ Yield: 82%. Given the instability of this compound on silica gel, purification by flash column chromatography was not possible. Copies of the NMR spectra of the crude material are attached with the relevant signals highlighted. **HRMS** (ESI+) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{H}^+$: 235.1710 [$M+\text{H}$] $^+$; found 235.1618.

8. Copy of NMR spectra

H

^{19}F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3)

3

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

8

^{19}F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3)

9

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

10

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

11

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

12

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

20

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD)

21

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD)

21

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD)

21

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD)

22

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD)

23

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD)

23

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD)

23

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD)

25

^{19}F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3)

29

^{19}F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl_3)

35

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, DMSO-d₆)

37

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

40

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD)

40

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD)

42

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD)

42

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD)

42

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CD₃OD)

43

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

46

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

47

¹⁹F NMR (376.5 MHz, CDCl₃)

48

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD)

48

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD)

9. X-Ray structures of compounds 5, 10 and 15

CCDC 2355446, 2355451 and 2355434 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for compounds **5**, **10** and **15** respectively. These data are provided free of charge by the joint Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and Fachinformationszentrum Karlsruhe Access Structures service

9.1 The X-ray structure of compound 5

Single crystals for X-Ray analysis were crystallised by slow evaporation from ethyl acetate. A colourless tabular crystal, approximate dimensions 0.200 mm × 0.330 mm × 0.850 mm, was used for the X-ray crystallographic analysis. The X-ray intensity data were measured on a Bruker X8 Apex2 system equipped with a graphite monochromator and a sealed tube molybdenum source ($\lambda = 0.71073\text{\AA}$). The data have been acquired in air at room temperature. A total of 1100 frames were collected. The total exposure time was 19.68 hours. The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package. The integration of the data using a monoclinic unit cell yielded a total of 11514 reflections to a maximum θ angle of 26.4° , of which 3889 were independent (average redundancy 13.06, completeness = 99.2%, $R_{\text{int}} = 3.53\%$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 3.52\%$) and 2662 (68.45%) were greater than $2\sigma(F^2)$.

The final cell constants of $a = 8.7854(5)\text{\AA}$, $b = 9.2084(5)\text{\AA}$, $c = 12.1625(7)\text{\AA}$, $\alpha = 88.540(3)$, $\beta = 88.728(3)^\circ$, $\gamma = 77.067(3)$, $V = 958.09(9)\text{\AA}^3$, are based upon the refinement of the XYZ-centroids of 4140 reflections above $20\sigma(I)$ with $2.8^\circ < 2\theta < 27.9^\circ$. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the multi-scan method (SADABS). The ratio of minimum to maximum apparent transmission was 0.837. The calculated minimum and maximum transmission coefficients (based on crystal size) are 0.936 and 0.985.

The final anisotropic full-matrix least-squares refinement on F^2 with 217 variables converged at $R_1 = 6.85\%$, for the observed data and $wR_2 = 11.47\%$ for all data. The goodness-of-fit was 0.944. The largest peak in the final difference electron density synthesis was $0.27\text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^3$ and the largest hole was $-0.27\text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^3$. On the basis of the final model, the calculated density was 1.152 g/cm^3 and $F(000)$, 360 e^- .

Table 1. Sample and crystal data for compound 5.

$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	$Z = 2$
$M_r = 332.44$	$F(000) = 360$
Triclinic, $P\bar{1}$	$D_x = 1.152\text{ Mg m}^{-3}$
Hall symbol: -P 1	Mo $K\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 0.71073\text{\AA}$
$a = 8.7854(5)\text{\AA}$	Cell parameters from 4140 reflections
$b = 9.2084(5)\text{\AA}$	$\theta = 2.8\text{--}27.9^\circ$
$c = 12.1625(7)\text{\AA}$	$\mu = 0.08\text{ mm}^{-1}$
$\alpha = 88.540(3)^\circ$	$T = 293\text{ K}$
$\beta = 87.728(3)^\circ$	Tabular, colourless
$\gamma = 77.067(3)^\circ$	$0.85 \times 0.33 \times 0.20\text{ mm}$
$V = 958.09(9)\text{\AA}^3$	

Table 2. Data collection and structure refinement for compound 5.

Bruker X8 diffractometer	3889 independent reflections
Radiation source: MoKalpha	2662 reflections with $I > 2.0\sigma(I)$
Graphite monochromator	$R_{\text{int}} = 0.035$
ϕ & ω scans	$\theta_{\text{max}} = 26.4^\circ$, $\theta_{\text{min}} = 1.7^\circ$
Absorption correction: multi-scan SADABS	$h = -10 \rightarrow 7$
$T_{\text{min}} = 0.82$, $T_{\text{max}} = 0.98$	$k = -11 \rightarrow 11$
11514 measured reflections	$l = -15 \rightarrow 15$
Refinement on F^2	Primary atom site location: iterative
Least-squares matrix: full	Hydrogen site location: difference Fourier map
$R[F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)] = 0.044$	H-atom parameters constrained
$wR(F^2) = 0.115$	Method = Modified Sheldrick $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.04P)^2 + 0.27P]$, where $P = (\max(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2)/3$
$S = 0.94$	$(\Delta/\sigma)_{\text{max}} = 0.0002$
3873 reflections	$\Delta\rho_{\text{max}} = 0.27 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$
217 parameters	$\Delta\rho_{\text{min}} = -0.27 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$
0 restraints	

Table 3. Fractional atomic coordinates and isotropic or equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) for compound 5.

	x	y	z	$U_{\text{iso}}^*/U_{\text{eq}}$
C1	0.53913 (17)	0.84861 (18)	-0.16566 (12)	0.0479
C2	0.5391 (2)	0.7456 (2)	-0.25989 (16)	0.074
C3	0.4882 (2)	1.0111 (2)	-0.19798 (16)	0.0667
C4	0.69703 (19)	0.8192 (2)	-0.11315 (15)	0.0661
C5	0.05935 (18)	0.7648 (2)	0.02496 (13)	0.0579
C6	0.11358 (17)	0.68422 (17)	0.13300 (13)	0.048
C7	0.28246 (18)	0.6900 (2)	0.09783 (13)	0.0555
C8	0.03692 (17)	0.73855 (17)	0.24392 (12)	0.0451
C9	-0.12912 (19)	0.54960 (19)	0.28913 (14)	0.0549
C10	-0.1002 (2)	0.3813 (2)	0.30719 (18)	0.0763
C11	-0.2407 (2)	0.6000 (2)	0.19617 (19)	0.0835
C12	-0.1906 (3)	0.6299 (3)	0.39547 (18)	0.0869
C13	0.12721 (17)	0.80261 (18)	0.32516 (12)	0.0468
C14	0.2502 (2)	0.7122 (2)	0.37977 (14)	0.0621
C15	0.3328 (2)	0.7734 (3)	0.45401 (15)	0.0725
C16	0.2930 (2)	0.9238 (3)	0.47382 (15)	0.0732

C17	0.1728 (2)	1.0129 (2)	0.41963 (16)	0.0709
C18	0.0895 (2)	0.95350 (19)	0.34571 (14)	0.0568
C19	0.28253 (17)	0.83281 (19)	-0.08496 (13)	0.0495
N1	0.21855 (16)	0.7818 (2)	0.00458 (13)	0.0787
N2	0.02760 (14)	0.58132 (14)	0.26908 (11)	0.0495
O1	0.43778 (11)	0.80969 (12)	-0.07498 (8)	0.0514
O2	0.20739 (13)	0.89419 (15)	-0.16068 (9)	0.0661
O3	0.08224 (15)	0.54015 (13)	0.15356 (10)	0.0689
H52	-0.0173	0.8629	0.0336	0.0747*
H51	0.0249	0.6982	-0.0288	0.0738*
H71	0.3363	0.7451	0.1494	0.0697*
H72	0.3509	0.5903	0.0787	0.0708*
H81	-0.0700	0.8115	0.2312	0.0574*
H181	0.0028	1.0172	0.3053	0.0737*
H171	0.1446	1.122	0.4333	0.0875*
H161	0.3501	0.966	0.5271	0.0923*
H151	0.4194	0.7086	0.4946	0.0906*
H141	0.275	0.6038	0.3656	0.0787*
H101	-0.2017	0.357	0.3235	0.1161*
H103	-0.0274	0.353	0.3696	0.1167*
H102	-0.0579	0.3356	0.2373	0.1167*
H122	-0.2820	0.5951	0.4204	0.1349*
H123	-0.2207	0.7384	0.3794	0.1343*
H121	-0.1079	0.6058	0.4516	0.1359*
H112	-0.3409	0.582	0.2218	0.1277*
H113	-0.2479	0.7064	0.1801	0.1271*
H111	-0.2010	0.5408	0.1294	0.1272*
H33	0.5703	1.0373	-0.2466	0.1000*
H32	0.4795	1.0708	-0.1287	0.1002*
H31	0.3871	1.03	-0.2362	0.1000*
H43	0.7696	0.842	-0.1691	0.1040*
H42	0.6878	0.8907	-0.0500	0.1046*
H41	0.7261	0.7135	-0.0887	0.1049*
H23	0.6144	0.7631	-0.3165	0.1147*
H22	0.4345	0.7668	-0.2925	0.1151*
H21	0.5706	0.6395	-0.2354	0.1156*

Table 4. Atomic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) for compound 5.

	U^{11}	U^{22}	U^{33}	U^{12}	U^{13}	U^{23}
C1	0.0451 (8)	0.0555 (10)	0.0436 (9)	-0.0139 (7)	0.0070 (7)	-0.0004 (7)
C2	0.0825 (13)	0.0821 (14)	0.0600 (12)	-0.0239 (11)	0.0070 (10)	-0.0182 (10)
C3	0.0676 (11)	0.0613 (11)	0.0719 (12)	-0.0193 (9)	0.0111 (9)	0.0082 (9)
C4	0.0455 (9)	0.0873 (14)	0.0657 (12)	-0.0166 (9)	0.0034 (8)	-0.0004 (10)
C5	0.0432 (8)	0.0837 (13)	0.0513 (10)	-0.0239 (8)	-0.0003 (7)	-0.0026 (9)
C6	0.0470 (8)	0.0483 (9)	0.0515 (9)	-0.0174 (7)	0.0057 (7)	-0.0032 (7)
C7	0.0454 (8)	0.0686 (11)	0.0525 (10)	-0.0144 (8)	0.0005 (7)	0.0103 (8)
C8	0.0447 (8)	0.0443 (9)	0.0470 (9)	-0.0122 (6)	0.0022 (6)	0.0007 (7)
C9	0.0503 (9)	0.0610 (11)	0.0586 (10)	-0.0245 (8)	0.0094 (7)	-0.0090 (8)
C10	0.0877 (14)	0.0683 (13)	0.0832 (14)	-0.0414 (11)	0.0096 (11)	-0.0019 (11)
C11	0.0611 (11)	0.0859 (15)	0.1060 (17)	-0.0174 (10)	-0.0202 (11)	-0.0144 (12)
C12	0.0856 (14)	0.1003 (16)	0.0824 (15)	-0.0409 (12)	0.0381 (12)	-0.0284 (12)
C13	0.0486 (8)	0.0528 (10)	0.0415 (8)	-0.0181 (7)	0.0058 (6)	-0.0004 (7)
C14	0.0635 (10)	0.0648 (12)	0.0597 (11)	-0.0175 (9)	-0.0070 (9)	0.0017 (9)
C15	0.0678 (12)	0.0989 (17)	0.0550 (11)	-0.0265 (11)	-0.0112 (9)	0.0064 (11)
C16	0.0814 (13)	0.1004 (17)	0.0505 (11)	-0.0467 (12)	0.0036 (10)	-0.0141 (11)
C17	0.0831 (13)	0.0707 (13)	0.0649 (12)	-0.0301 (11)	0.0071 (10)	-0.0171 (10)
C18	0.0617 (10)	0.0563 (11)	0.0550 (10)	-0.0190 (8)	0.0059 (8)	-0.0076 (8)
C19	0.0447 (8)	0.0623 (10)	0.0434 (9)	-0.0158 (7)	-0.0043 (7)	0.0008 (8)
N1	0.0422 (7)	0.1352 (15)	0.0617 (10)	-0.0302 (8)	-0.0066 (7)	0.0396 (10)
N2	0.0483 (7)	0.0482 (8)	0.0535 (8)	-0.0152 (6)	0.0070 (6)	-0.0027 (6)
O1	0.0420 (5)	0.0689 (7)	0.0450 (6)	-0.0172 (5)	-0.0019 (4)	0.0090 (5)
O2	0.0518 (7)	0.0956 (10)	0.0513 (7)	-0.0171 (6)	-0.0095 (5)	0.0142 (6)
O3	0.0814 (8)	0.0547 (7)	0.0733 (8)	-0.0255 (6)	0.0355 (7)	-0.0183 (6)

Table 5. Geometric parameters ($\text{\AA}$, $^\circ$) for compound 5.

C1—C2	1.506 (2)	C9—C11	1.521 (3)
C1—C3	1.510 (2)	C9—C12	1.525 (2)
C1—C4	1.516 (2)	C9—N2	1.4800 (19)
C1—O1	1.4773 (18)	C10—H101	0.978
C2—H23	0.972	C10—H103	1.004
C2—H22	0.992	C10—H102	0.981

C2—H21	0.995	C11—H112	0.97
C3—H33	0.982	C11—H113	0.983
C3—H32	1.009	C11—H111	0.997
C3—H31	0.997	C12—H122	0.965
C4—H43	0.966	C12—H123	0.991
C4—H42	1.014	C12—H121	1.001
C4—H41	0.99	C13—C14	1.389 (2)
C5—C6	1.532 (2)	C13—C18	1.381 (2)
C5—N1	1.453 (2)	C14—C15	1.386 (2)
C5—H52	1.003	C14—H141	0.991
C5—H51	1.007	C15—C16	1.375 (3)
C6—C7	1.540 (2)	C15—H151	0.995
C6—C8	1.528 (2)	C16—C17	1.364 (3)
C6—O3	1.4280 (19)	C16—H161	0.975
C7—N1	1.451 (2)	C17—C18	1.378 (2)
C7—H71	1.011	C17—H171	0.997
C7—H72	1.006	C18—H181	0.991
C8—C13	1.502 (2)	C19—N1	1.329 (2)
C8—N2	1.4916 (19)	C19—O1	1.3424 (17)
C8—H81	1.04	C19—O2	1.2076 (18)
C9—C10	1.525 (2)	N2—O3	1.4968 (17)
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C2—C1—C3	112.98 (15)	C10—C9—N2	105.33 (14)
C2—C1—C4	111.59 (14)	C11—C9—N2	114.21 (15)

C3—C1—C4	110.23 (14)	C12—C9—N2	104.59 (13)
C2—C1—O1	108.61 (13)	C9—C10—H101	107.3
C3—C1—O1	110.86 (12)	C9—C10—H103	108.2
C4—C1—O1	102.02 (12)	H101—C10—H103	112.1
C1—C2—H23	109	C9—C10—H102	106.8
C1—C2—H22	110	H101—C10—H102	108.5
H23—C2—H22	108	H103—C10—H102	113.5
C1—C2—H21	110.9	C9—C11—H112	106.3
H23—C2—H21	107.8	C9—C11—H113	109.4
H22—C2—H21	111	H112—C11—H113	111.2
C1—C3—H33	108.2	C9—C11—H111	109.3
C1—C3—H32	107.5	H112—C11—H111	110.8
H33—C3—H32	108.5	H113—C11—H111	109.8
C1—C3—H31	110.5	C9—C12—H122	107.4
H33—C3—H31	110.4	C9—C12—H123	108.7
H32—C3—H31	111.7	H122—C12—H123	109.2
C1—C4—H43	106.1	C9—C12—H121	109.2
C1—C4—H42	107.2	H122—C12—H121	110.5
H43—C4—H42	109.8	H123—C12—H121	111.7
C1—C4—H41	109.3	C8—C13—C14	120.85 (15)
H43—C4—H41	111.6	C8—C13—C18	120.12 (14)
H42—C4—H41	112.6	C14—C13—C18	119.03 (15)
C6—C5—N1	87.76 (11)	C13—C14—C15	120.06 (18)

C6—C5—H52	115	C13—C14—H141	118.4
N1—C5—H52	112.6	C15—C14—H141	121.5
C6—C5—H51	112.8	C14—C15—C16	120.04 (19)
N1—C5—H51	113.9	C14—C15—H151	120.3
H52—C5—H51	112.6	C16—C15—H151	119.6
C5—C6—C7	88.63 (12)	C15—C16—C17	119.96 (18)
C5—C6—C8	121.63 (13)	C15—C16—H161	119.7
C7—C6—C8	123.66 (13)	C17—C16—H161	120.3
C5—C6—O3	118.02 (13)	C16—C17—C18	120.62 (19)
C7—C6—O3	116.92 (13)	C16—C17—H171	120
C8—C6—O3	90.94 (11)	C18—C17—H171	119.3
C6—C7—N1	87.52 (11)	C13—C18—C17	120.29 (17)
C6—C7—H71	115.1	C13—C18—H181	118.3
N1—C7—H71	112.4	C17—C18—H181	121.4
C6—C7—H72	114	N1—C19—O1	109.73 (13)
N1—C7—H72	115.2	N1—C19—O2	123.27 (14)
H71—C7—H72	110.9	O1—C19—O2	126.96 (15)
C6—C8—C13	119.87 (12)	C5—N1—C7	95.28 (12)
C6—C8—N2	87.34 (11)	C5—N1—C19	129.31 (14)
C13—C8—N2	113.97 (12)	C7—N1—C19	133.44 (14)
C6—C8—H81	109.4	C8—N2—C9	117.90 (12)
C13—C8—H81	110	C8—N2—O3	89.75 (10)
N2—C8—H81	114.8	C9—N2—O3	108.91 (11)

C10—C9—C11	110.81 (15)	C1—O1—C19	121.05 (11)
C10—C9—C12	110.35 (16)	N2—O3—C6	90.92 (10)
C11—C9—C12	111.23 (16)		
H102—C10—H101	112.6	H201—C20—H203	110.1
C9—C11—N2	87.54 (19)	C8—N1—C17	118.2 (2)
C9—C11—H112	114	C8—N1—O1	89.04 (16)
N2—C11—H112	112.4	C17—N1—O1	110.03 (19)
C9—C11—H111	115.9	C11—N2—C10	94.2 (2)
N2—C11—H111	113.7	C11—N2—C12	130.3 (2)
H112—C11—H111	111.3	C10—N2—C12	126.8 (2)
N2—C12—O2	109.8 (2)	N1—O1—C9	89.74 (16)
N2—C12—O3	123.5 (2)	C13—O2—C12	121.07 (18)
O2—C12—O3	126.7 (2)		

Fig. 1. The asymmetric unit of compound **5** with labeling scheme and 50% probability ellipsoids. For the sake of clarity, the labels of hydrogen atoms are not represented.

Fig 2. 3D -packing viewed down the *c* axis for compound **5**.

9.2 The X-ray structure of compound 10

Single crystals for X-Ray analysis were crystallised by slow evaporation from diethyl ether. A translucent needle-like colorless crystal, approximate dimensions 0.015 mm x 0.020 mm x 1.000 mm, was used for the X-ray crystallographic analysis. The X-ray intensity data were measured on a Bruker D8 VENTURE PHOTON 100 CMOS system equipped with a mirror monochromator, a Cu-K α INCOATEC 1 μ S micro-focus source ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$) and a Cryostream-1000 (Oxford Cryosystems) cryostat. The data have been acquired at a temperature of 103 K. A total of 1678 frames were collected. The total exposure time was 4.80 hours. The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package using a narrow-frame algorithm. The integration of the data using a monoclinic unit cell yielded a total of 29066 reflections to a maximum θ angle of 68.68°, of which 3848 were independent (average redundancy 7.56, completeness = 99.7%, Rint = 9.00%) and 3827 (99.45%) were greater than $2\sigma(F^2)$.

The final cell constants of $a = 8.6029 (4) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 16.1176 (7) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 15.2114 (7) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 94.3858 (29)^\circ$, $V = 2100.90 (15) \text{ \AA}^3$, are based upon the refinement of the XYZ-centroids of 4948 reflections above $20 \sigma(I)$ with $2.91^\circ < 2\theta < 68.68^\circ$. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the multi-scan method (SADABS). The ratio of minimum to maximum apparent transmission was 0.848. The calculated minimum and maximum transmission coefficients (based on crystal size) are 0.419 and 0.987.

The final anisotropic full-matrix least-squares refinement on F^2 with 282 variables converged at $R1 = 7.92\%$, for the observed data and $wR2 = 17.57\%$ for all data. The goodness-of-fit was 0.940. The largest peak in the final difference electron density synthesis was $0.55 \text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^3$ and the largest hole was $-0.31 \text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^3$. On the basis of the final model, the calculated density was 1.266 g/cm^3 and $F(000)$, 848 e^- .

Table 6. Sample and crystal data for compound 10.

$C_{20}H_{27}F_{3.00}N_2O_3$	$F(000) = 848$
$M_r = 400.44$	$D_x = 1.266 \text{ Mg m}^{-3}$
Monoclinic, $P2_1/c$	Cu $K\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$
Hall symbol: $-P 2_1bc$	Cell parameters from 4948 reflections
$a = 15.2109 (6) \text{ \AA}$	$\theta = 2.9\text{--}68.7^\circ$
$b = 16.1042 (6) \text{ \AA}$	$\mu = 0.87 \text{ mm}^{-1}$
$c = 8.5991 (4) \text{ \AA}$	$T = 103 \text{ K}$
$\beta = 94.153 (3)^\circ$	Needle, translucent colourless
$V = 2100.90 (15) \text{ \AA}^3$	$1.00 \times 0.02 \times 0.02 \text{ mm}$
$Z = 4$	

Table 7. Data collection and structure refinement for compound 10.

Bruker D8 VENTURE diffractometer	2674 reflections with $I > 2.0\sigma(I)$
Montel layer optics monochromator	$R_{\text{int}} = 0.090$
ϕ & ω scans	$\theta_{\text{max}} = 68.4^\circ$, $\theta_{\text{min}} = 2.9^\circ$
Absorption correction: multi-scan	$h = -18 \rightarrow 18$

SADABS	
$T_{\min} = 0.84$, $T_{\max} = 0.99$	$k = -19 \rightarrow 19$
29066 measured reflections	$l = -10 \rightarrow 10$
3848 independent reflections	
Refinement on F^2	Hydrogen site location: difference Fourier map
Least-squares matrix: full	H-atom parameters constrained
$R[F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)] = 0.058$	Method = Modified Sheldrick $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.11P)^2 + 0.9P]$, where $P = (\max(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2)/3$
$wR(F^2) = 0.175$	$(\Delta/\sigma)_{\max} = 0.006$
$S = 0.94$	$\Delta\rho_{\max} = 0.55 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$
3827 reflections	$\Delta\rho_{\min} = -0.31 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$
282 parameters	Extinction correction: Larson (1970), Equation 22
54 restraints	Extinction coefficient: 80 (20)
Primary atom site location: structure-invariant direct methods	

Table 8. Fractional atomic coordinates and isotropic or equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) for compound 10.

	<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>z</i>	$U_{\text{iso}}^*/U_{\text{eq}}$	Occ. (<1)
C1	0.89789 (14)	0.34247 (13)	1.0020 (3)	0.0453	
C2	0.85953 (16)	0.39618 (15)	0.8732 (3)	0.0337	
C3	0.80651 (17)	0.36309 (15)	0.7501 (3)	0.0355	
C4	0.76970 (17)	0.41534 (15)	0.6337 (3)	0.0334	
C5	0.78742 (16)	0.50010 (15)	0.6384 (3)	0.0296	
C6	0.84227 (16)	0.53190 (14)	0.7621 (3)	0.0319	
C7	0.87740 (16)	0.48082 (15)	0.8790 (3)	0.0322	
C8	0.74531 (16)	0.55679 (15)	0.5148 (3)	0.0305	
C9	0.67329 (17)	0.61778 (15)	0.5551 (3)	0.0321	
C10	0.57525 (18)	0.60300 (19)	0.5029 (3)	0.0380	
C11	0.64632 (16)	0.63085 (15)	0.7230 (3)	0.0321	
C12	0.47983 (16)	0.61133 (15)	0.7289 (3)	0.0326	
C13	0.41777 (16)	0.63374 (15)	0.9814 (3)	0.0295	
C14	0.4638 (2)	0.6455 (2)	1.1418 (3)	0.0438	
C15	0.36673 (19)	0.55289 (16)	0.9724 (4)	0.0413	

C16	0.36023 (17)	0.70796 (16)	0.9346 (3)	0.0363	
C17	0.83849 (18)	0.63748 (16)	0.3311 (3)	0.0354	
C18	0.8724 (2)	0.7264 (2)	0.3233 (4)	0.0533	
C19	0.7743 (2)	0.62091 (19)	0.1900 (3)	0.0469	
C20	0.9130 (2)	0.5750 (2)	0.3432 (5)	0.0624	
N1	0.79960 (14)	0.63143 (12)	0.4837 (3)	0.0332	
N2	0.55778 (14)	0.60047 (16)	0.6686 (3)	0.0400	
O1	0.71743 (13)	0.68391 (11)	0.4829 (2)	0.0400	
O2	0.49248 (11)	0.62949 (10)	0.8818 (2)	0.0300	
O3	0.40907 (12)	0.60312 (12)	0.6536 (2)	0.0389	
F10	0.9849 (5)	0.3550 (10)	1.0275 (19)	0.0533	0.53 (6)
F11	0.9785 (8)	0.3668 (9)	1.061 (3)	0.0677	0.47 (6)
F20	0.8838 (12)	0.2618 (5)	0.9809 (18)	0.0645	0.53 (6)
F21	0.9024 (14)	0.2628 (5)	0.9597 (18)	0.0532	0.47 (6)
F30	0.8651 (12)	0.3605 (10)	1.1388 (10)	0.0523	0.53 (6)
F31	0.8481 (11)	0.3432 (14)	1.1259 (16)	0.0524	0.47 (6)
H31	0.7956	0.3063	0.7450	0.0431*	
H41	0.7333	0.3928	0.5514	0.0401*	
H61	0.8542	0.5893	0.7642	0.0375*	
H71	0.9131	0.5027	0.9597	0.0389*	
H81	0.7257	0.5248	0.4187	0.0375*	
H102	0.5477	0.6512	0.4479	0.0464*	
H101	0.5622	0.5505	0.4482	0.0456*	
H112	0.6458	0.6880	0.7550	0.0376*	
H111	0.6761	0.5963	0.8020	0.0385*	
H141	0.4953	0.6969	1.1454	0.0658*	
H143	0.4204	0.6467	1.2188	0.0656*	
H142	0.5043	0.5999	1.1643	0.0654*	
H151	0.3344	0.5459	0.8706	0.0619*	
H152	0.3248	0.5539	1.0500	0.0617*	
H153	0.4066	0.5057	0.9936	0.0616*	
H162	0.3330	0.6994	0.8304	0.0542*	
H161	0.3955	0.7586	0.9385	0.0536*	
H163	0.3147	0.7128	1.0078	0.0535*	

H182	0.9114	0.7372	0.4116	0.0801*
H181	0.9044	0.7334	0.2306	0.0798*
H183	0.8235	0.7643	0.3213	0.0798*
H192	0.7572	0.5639	0.1863	0.0701*
H191	0.8009	0.6337	0.0946	0.0691*
H193	0.7218	0.6554	0.1958	0.0697*
H202	0.8890	0.5188	0.3474	0.0921*
H201	0.9525	0.5865	0.4357	0.0929*
H203	0.9445	0.5817	0.2487	0.0924*

Table 9. Atomic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) for compound 10.

	U^{11}	U^{22}	U^{33}	U^{12}	U^{13}	U^{23}
C1	0.0378 (13)	0.0346 (14)	0.0620 (18)	-0.0025 (11)	-0.0066 (12)	0.0114 (13)
C2	0.0302 (12)	0.0272 (12)	0.0437 (15)	0.0035 (9)	0.0027 (10)	0.0063 (11)
C3	0.0398 (14)	0.0204 (11)	0.0464 (16)	-0.0028 (10)	0.0037 (11)	-0.0021 (10)
C4	0.0379 (13)	0.0265 (12)	0.0356 (14)	-0.0043 (10)	0.0009 (10)	-0.0034 (10)
C5	0.0324 (12)	0.0248 (11)	0.0317 (12)	-0.0008 (9)	0.0018 (9)	-0.0010 (9)
C6	0.0370 (13)	0.0200 (11)	0.0381 (14)	-0.0008 (9)	-0.0006 (10)	-0.0016 (10)
C7	0.0294 (12)	0.0276 (12)	0.0389 (14)	-0.0009 (9)	-0.0033 (10)	-0.0008 (10)
C8	0.0352 (12)	0.0242 (11)	0.0322 (13)	-0.0017 (9)	0.0015 (10)	-0.0018 (9)
C9	0.0380 (13)	0.0255 (12)	0.0331 (13)	0.0010 (10)	0.0038 (10)	0.0015 (10)
C10	0.0400 (14)	0.0467 (15)	0.0266 (13)	0.0076 (12)	-0.0019 (10)	-0.0002 (11)
C11	0.0329 (12)	0.0318 (12)	0.0312 (13)	-0.0007 (10)	-0.0002 (10)	-0.0025 (10)
C12	0.0321 (13)	0.0311 (12)	0.0339 (14)	0.0036 (10)	-0.0027 (10)	-0.0043 (10)
C13	0.0320 (12)	0.0280 (12)	0.0281 (13)	0.0032 (9)	0.0006 (9)	-0.0002 (9)
C14	0.0478 (16)	0.0518 (17)	0.0313 (14)	0.0095 (13)	-0.0009 (11)	-0.0061 (12)
C15	0.0451 (15)	0.0291 (13)	0.0508 (17)	0.0009 (11)	0.0099 (12)	0.0021 (12)
C16	0.0382 (13)	0.0274 (12)	0.0433 (15)	0.0076 (10)	0.0029 (11)	0.0031 (11)
C17	0.0423 (14)	0.0305 (13)	0.0337 (14)	-0.0060 (10)	0.0041 (11)	-0.0007 (10)
C18	0.072 (2)	0.0475 (18)	0.0406 (17)	-0.0271 (16)	0.0051 (14)	0.0037 (13)
C19	0.068 (2)	0.0428 (16)	0.0301 (14)	-0.0160 (14)	0.0043 (13)	-0.0019 (12)
C20	0.059 (2)	0.066 (2)	0.065 (2)	0.0132 (17)	0.0254 (17)	0.0112 (18)

N1	0.0401 (12)	0.0245 (10)	0.0352 (12)	-0.0018 (8)	0.0045 (9)	0.0006 (8)
N2	0.0314 (11)	0.0584 (15)	0.0295 (12)	0.0015 (10)	-0.0022 (8)	-0.0066 (10)
O1	0.0525 (11)	0.0243 (9)	0.0445 (11)	0.0047 (8)	0.0121 (8)	0.0046 (8)
O2	0.0298 (9)	0.0340 (9)	0.0255 (9)	0.0014 (7)	-0.0019 (6)	-0.0030 (7)
O3	0.0334 (9)	0.0448 (10)	0.0369 (10)	0.0037 (8)	-0.0074 (7)	-0.0055 (8)
F10	0.035 (2)	0.049 (4)	0.073 (5)	0.005 (2)	-0.014 (2)	0.029 (3)
F11	0.042 (3)	0.041 (3)	0.115 (6)	-0.006 (3)	-0.026 (3)	0.015 (4)
F20	0.068 (4)	0.038 (3)	0.087 (4)	0.002 (2)	0.002 (4)	0.026 (3)
F21	0.068 (5)	0.019 (3)	0.069 (4)	0.005 (2)	-0.018 (3)	0.007 (3)
F30	0.060 (4)	0.045 (4)	0.050 (2)	-0.011 (3)	-0.014 (2)	0.011 (2)
F31	0.048 (4)	0.055 (5)	0.052 (3)	-0.017 (3)	-0.013 (3)	0.022 (3)

Table 10. Geometric parameters ($\text{\AA}$, $^\circ$) for compound 10.

C1—C2	1.491 (3)	C12—N2	1.339 (3)
C1—F10	1.342 (7)	C12—O2	1.347 (3)
C1—F20	1.327 (7)	C12—O3	1.222 (3)
C1—F30	1.343 (7)	C13—C14	1.512 (4)
C1—C2	1.491 (3)	C13—C15	1.515 (3)
C1—F11	1.350 (8)	C13—C16	1.518 (3)
C1—F21	1.337 (7)	C13—O2	1.474 (3)
C1—F31	1.351 (8)	C14—H141	0.955
C2—C3	1.389 (4)	C14—H143	0.968
C2—C7	1.390 (3)	C14—H142	0.969
C3—C4	1.394 (4)	C15—H151	0.979
C3—H31	0.929	C15—H152	0.957
C4—C5	1.391 (3)	C15—H153	0.982

C4—H41	0.939	C16—H162	0.97
C5—C6	1.401 (3)	C16—H161	0.976
C5—C8	1.508 (3)	C16—H163	0.972
C6—C7	1.377 (4)	C17—C18	1.524 (4)
C6—H61	0.942	C17—C19	1.525 (4)
C7—H71	0.92	C17—C20	1.514 (4)
C8—C9	1.530 (3)	C17—N1	1.481 (3)
C8—N1	1.493 (3)	C18—H182	0.946
C8—H81	1	C18—H181	0.971
C9—C10	1.544 (4)	C18—H183	0.962
C9—C11	1.544 (4)	C19—H192	0.954
C9—O1	1.425 (3)	C19—H191	0.962
C10—N2	1.469 (4)	C19—H193	0.977
C10—H102	0.987	C20—H202	0.976
C10—H101	0.98	C20—H201	0.979
C11—N2	1.477 (3)	C20—H203	0.979
C11—H112	0.96	N1—O1	1.508 (3)
C11—H111	0.966		
<hr/>			
C2—C1—F10	111.3 (4)	C14—C13—C15	110.9 (2)
C2—C1—F20	114.5 (5)	C14—C13—C16	111.3 (2)
F10—C1—F20	108.47 (10)	C15—C13—C16	112.3 (2)
C2—C1—F30	112.0 (5)	C14—C13—O2	102.14 (19)
F10—C1—F30	104.45 (10)	C15—C13—O2	110.1 (2)

F20—C1—F30	105.39 (10)	C16—C13—O2	109.7 (2)
C2—C1—F11	113.9 (6)	C13—C14—H141	109.7
C2—C1—F21	112.3 (6)	C13—C14—H143	109.5
F11—C1—F21	108.46 (10)	H141—C14—H143	109
C2—C1—F31	111.7 (6)	C13—C14—H142	109.4
F11—C1—F31	104.40 (10)	H141—C14—H142	109.8
F21—C1—F31	105.42 (10)	H143—C14—H142	109.5
C1—C2—C3	121.2 (2)	C13—C15—H151	111.6
C1—C2—C7	118.5 (2)	C13—C15—H152	108.4
C3—C2—C7	120.3 (2)	H151—C15—H152	108
C2—C3—C4	119.8 (2)	C13—C15—H153	110.4
C2—C3—H31	120.3	H151—C15—H153	109.9
C4—C3—H31	119.9	H152—C15—H153	108.5
C3—C4—C5	120.3 (2)	C13—C16—H162	109.4
C3—C4—H41	119.5	C13—C16—H161	110.2
C5—C4—H41	120.2	H162—C16—H161	110.4
C4—C5—C6	119.0 (2)	C13—C16—H163	108.4
C4—C5—C8	120.1 (2)	H162—C16—H163	109.5
C6—C5—C8	120.9 (2)	H161—C16—H163	109
C5—C6—C7	121.0 (2)	C18—C17—C19	109.2 (2)
C5—C6—H61	118.4	C18—C17—C20	112.0 (3)
C7—C6—H61	120.6	C19—C17—C20	111.8 (3)
C2—C7—C6	119.7 (2)	C18—C17—N1	105.0 (2)

C2—C7—H71	120.5	C19—C17—N1	114.8 (2)
C6—C7—H71	119.9	C20—C17—N1	103.9 (2)
C5—C8—C9	120.2 (2)	C17—C18—H182	109.4
C5—C8—N1	113.6 (2)	C17—C18—H181	109.7
C9—C8—N1	86.45 (18)	H182—C18—H181	108.4
C5—C8—H81	110.9	C17—C18—H183	109.5
C9—C8—H81	110	H182—C18—H183	109.7
N1—C8—H81	113.7	H181—C18—H183	110.1
C8—C9—C10	121.8 (2)	C17—C19—H192	110.6
C8—C9—C11	122.9 (2)	C17—C19—H191	110.9
C10—C9—C11	88.65 (19)	H192—C19—H191	107.9
C8—C9—O1	90.76 (19)	C17—C19—H193	109.8
C10—C9—O1	117.6 (2)	H192—C19—H193	109.1
C11—C9—O1	118.1 (2)	H191—C19—H193	108.5
C9—C10—N2	87.77 (19)	C17—C20—H202	109.8
C9—C10—H102	112.7	C17—C20—H201	110
N2—C10—H102	112.7	H202—C20—H201	110.8
C9—C10—H101	115.5	C17—C20—H203	106.2
N2—C10—H101	113.4	H202—C20—H203	109.9
H102—C10—H101	112.6	H201—C20—H203	110.1
C9—C11—N2	87.54 (19)	C8—N1—C17	118.2 (2)
C9—C11—H112	114	C8—N1—O1	89.04 (16)
N2—C11—H112	112.4	C17—N1—O1	110.03 (19)

C9—C11—H111	115.9	C11—N2—C10	94.2 (2)
N2—C11—H111	113.7	C11—N2—C12	130.3 (2)
H112—C11—H111	111.3	C10—N2—C12	126.8 (2)
N2—C12—O2	109.8 (2)	N1—O1—C9	89.74 (16)
N2—C12—O3	123.5 (2)	C13—O2—C12	121.07 (18)
O2—C12—O3	126.7 (2)		

Fig. 3. The asymmetric unit of compound **10** with labeling scheme and 50% probability ellipsoids. For the sake of clarity, the labels of hydrogen atoms are not represented.

Fig 4.3D- packing viewed down the *c* axis for compound **10**.

9.3 The X-ray structure of compound 15

Single crystals for X-Ray analysis were crystallised by slow evaporation from diethyl ether. A colourless tabular crystal, approximate dimensions $0.100 \text{ mm} \times 0.270 \text{ mm} \times 0.410 \text{ mm}$, was used for the X-ray crystallographic analysis. The X-ray intensity data were measured on a Bruker X8 Apex2 system equipped with a graphite monochromator and a sealed tube molybdenum source ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The data have been acquired in air at room temperature. A total of 815 frames were collected. The total exposure time was 28.18 hours. The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package. The integration of the data using a monoclinic unit cell yielded a total of 15381 reflections to a maximum θ angle of 23.3° , of which 5850 were independent ((average redundancy 19.56, completeness = 99.6%, $R_{\text{int}} = 2.96\%$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 4.14\%$) and 3860 (65.98%) were greater than $2\sigma(F^2)$.

The final cell constants of $a = 8.8225 (3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 12.8257 (4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 19.6675 (6) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 83.070 (2)^\circ$, $\beta = 78.796 (2)^\circ$, $\gamma = 69.750 (3)^\circ$, $V = 2044.67 (12) \text{ \AA}^3$, are based upon the refinement of the XYZ-centroids of 4140 reflections above $20 \sigma(I)$ with $2.8^\circ < 2\theta < 27.9^\circ$. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the multi-scan method (SADABS). The ratio of minimum to maximum apparent transmission was 0.898. The calculated minimum and maximum transmission coefficients (based on crystal size) are 0.890 and 0.990.

The final anisotropic full-matrix least-squares refinement on F^2 with 469 variables converged at $R_1 = 8.20\%$, for the observed data and $wR_2 = 11.30\%$ for all data. The goodness-of-fit was 0.974. The largest peak in the final difference electron density synthesis was $0.39 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$ and the largest hole was $-0.39 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$. On the basis of the final model, the calculated density was $1.177 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$ and $F(000)$, 784 e^- , with two molecules of **15** present in the asymmetric unit of the crystal structure.

Table 11. Sample and crystal data for compound 15.

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$	$Z = 4$
$M_r = 362.47$	$F(000) = 784$
Triclinic, $P\bar{1}$	$D_x = 1.177 \text{ Mg m}^{-3}$
Hall symbol: -P 1	Mo $K\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$
$a = 8.8225 (3) \text{ \AA}$	Cell parameters from 3505 reflections
$b = 12.8257 (4) \text{ \AA}$	$\theta = 2.5\text{--}22.5^\circ$
$c = 19.6675 (6) \text{ \AA}$	$\mu = 0.08 \text{ mm}^{-1}$
$\alpha = 83.070 (2)^\circ$	$T = 293 \text{ K}$
$\beta = 78.796 (2)^\circ$	Tabular, colourless
$\gamma = 69.750 (2)^\circ$	$0.41 \times 0.27 \times 0.10 \text{ mm}$
$V = 2044.67 (12) \text{ \AA}^3$	

Table 12. Data collection and structure refinement for 15.

Bruker X8 diffractometer	5850 independent reflections
Radiation source: MoK α	3860 reflections with $I > 2.0\sigma(I)$
Graphite monochromator	$R_{\text{int}} = 0.000$
ϕ & ω scans	$\theta_{\text{max}} = 23.3^\circ$, $\theta_{\text{min}} = 1.7^\circ$
Absorption correction: multi-scan SADABS	$h = -9 \rightarrow 9$
$T_{\text{min}} = 0.89$, $T_{\text{max}} = 0.99$	$k = -14 \rightarrow 12$
15381 measured reflections	$l = -21 \rightarrow 21$
Refinement on F^2	Primary atom site location: iterative
Least-squares matrix: full	Hydrogen site location: difference Fourier map
$R[F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)] = 0.046$	H-atom parameters constrained
$wR(F^2) = 0.113$	Method = Modified Sheldrick $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.04P)^2 + 0.99P]$, where $P = (\max(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2)/3$
$S = 0.97$	$(\Delta/\sigma)_{\text{max}} = 0.001$
5817 reflections	$\Delta\rho_{\text{max}} = 0.35 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$
469 parameters	$\Delta\rho_{\text{min}} = -0.39 \text{ e } \text{\AA}^{-3}$
0 restraints	

Table 13. Fractional atomic coordinates and isotropic or equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) for compound 15.

	x	y	z	$U_{\text{iso}}^*/U_{\text{eq}}$
C1	0.6486 (4)	0.4900 (2)	1.38564 (15)	0.0688
C2	0.6779 (3)	0.3596 (2)	1.30229 (12)	0.0418
C3	0.7565 (3)	0.2536 (2)	1.27913 (13)	0.053
C4	0.7133 (3)	0.2234 (2)	1.22261 (13)	0.0516
C5	0.5934 (3)	0.2975 (2)	1.18730 (12)	0.0385
C6	0.5204 (3)	0.4027 (2)	1.21049 (13)	0.0435
C7	0.5611 (3)	0.4348 (2)	1.26728 (13)	0.045
C8	0.5443 (3)	0.2656 (2)	1.12598 (12)	0.0404
C9	0.6587 (3)	0.2503 (2)	1.05598 (12)	0.0435
C10	0.8229 (3)	0.2720 (2)	1.04095 (13)	0.0498
C11	0.6093 (3)	0.3274 (2)	0.99218 (13)	0.0523
C12	0.8307 (3)	0.3994 (2)	0.93141 (13)	0.0443
C13	1.0931 (3)	0.4229 (2)	0.87894 (13)	0.0488
C14	1.0223 (4)	0.5477 (3)	0.86863 (17)	0.0771
C15	1.2509 (4)	0.3904 (3)	0.90780 (18)	0.09
C16	1.1155 (4)	0.3657 (3)	0.81367 (16)	0.0837

C17	0.4140 (3)	0.1178 (2)	1.12310 (13)	0.0502
C18	0.3045 (4)	0.1506 (3)	1.19225 (15)	0.0739
C19	0.4710 (4)	-0.0081 (2)	1.11689 (16)	0.0728
C20	0.3266 (4)	0.1789 (3)	1.06277 (16)	0.0709
C21	1.0377 (4)	0.0703 (3)	0.88580 (16)	0.0821
C22	0.8602 (3)	0.1545 (2)	0.80206 (13)	0.0465
C23	0.9202 (3)	0.0626 (2)	0.76320 (13)	0.0468
C24	0.8518 (3)	0.0598 (2)	0.70629 (13)	0.0446
C25	0.7236 (3)	0.1475 (2)	0.68673 (12)	0.0388
C26	0.6655 (4)	0.2404 (2)	0.72577 (14)	0.0577
C27	0.7328 (4)	0.2451 (2)	0.78241 (15)	0.0625
C28	0.6490 (3)	0.1408 (2)	0.62545 (12)	0.0388
C29	0.6859 (3)	0.2021 (2)	0.55579 (13)	0.0427
C30	0.7925 (3)	0.1396 (2)	0.49218 (13)	0.0507
C31	0.7928 (3)	0.2773 (2)	0.54430 (13)	0.0479
C32	1.0137 (3)	0.2176 (2)	0.43837 (13)	0.0462
C33	1.1768 (3)	0.3398 (2)	0.39392 (13)	0.0504
C34	1.3382 (4)	0.2464 (3)	0.38440 (17)	0.0732
C35	1.1105 (4)	0.3775 (3)	0.32656 (15)	0.0728
C36	1.1915 (5)	0.4368 (3)	0.42632 (17)	0.0872
C37	0.3507 (3)	0.1560 (2)	0.63164 (13)	0.048
C38	0.1879 (3)	0.2474 (3)	0.62651 (16)	0.0686
C39	0.3899 (4)	0.0727 (3)	0.57665 (16)	0.0752
C40	0.3484 (4)	0.0971 (3)	0.70381 (15)	0.0734
O1	0.7220 (2)	0.38078 (15)	1.36101 (9)	0.0581
O2	0.6663 (2)	0.13669 (15)	1.05650 (9)	0.0579
O3	0.7607 (2)	0.44856 (17)	0.88335 (10)	0.0625
O4	0.9872 (2)	0.38172 (15)	0.93563 (8)	0.0509
O5	0.9155 (2)	0.16453 (16)	0.86068 (10)	0.0677
O6	0.5135 (2)	0.25536 (16)	0.55439 (9)	0.0561
O7	1.0666 (2)	0.15790 (16)	0.38966 (10)	0.064
O8	1.0558 (2)	0.30581 (15)	0.44666 (8)	0.0516
N1	0.5633 (3)	0.14439 (17)	1.12728 (10)	0.0458
N2	0.7554 (3)	0.35908 (19)	0.98878 (11)	0.0503
N3	0.4739 (2)	0.21255 (17)	0.62772 (10)	0.0427
N4	0.9067 (3)	0.19962 (18)	0.49361 (11)	0.049
H101	0.8514	0.2985	1.081	0.0657*
H102	0.9141	0.2048	1.021	0.0652*
H112	0.503	0.3907	1.0005	0.0678*
H111	0.6137	0.2835	0.9523	0.0678*
H81	0.4287	0.3177	1.1197	0.0523*
H61	0.4385	0.4558	1.1859	0.0573*
H71	0.5085	0.5093	1.2827	0.0578*
H11	0.7019	0.4927	1.4247	0.1060*

H13	0.5309	0.504	1.4016	0.1066*
H12	0.6645	0.5456	1.3477	0.1065*
H31	0.8419	0.2015	1.3028	0.0651*
H41	0.767	0.149	1.2069	0.0643*
H202	0.2323	0.1542	1.066	0.1089*
H201	0.2908	0.2604	1.0668	0.1089*
H203	0.4034	0.1563	1.0195	0.1091*
H192	0.3765	-0.0284	1.1131	0.1121*
H193	0.5174	-0.0466	1.1578	0.1121*
H191	0.5527	-0.0267	1.0752	0.1119*
H183	0.2072	0.1285	1.1958	0.1114*
H182	0.3673	0.1128	1.2298	0.1112*
H181	0.271	0.2319	1.1943	0.1114*
H162	1.1995	0.3847	0.7797	0.1269*
H161	1.1492	0.2857	0.8257	0.1271*
H163	1.0117	0.3906	0.7968	0.1273*
H141	1.1055	0.573	0.8378	0.1161*
H143	0.9969	0.5795	0.9142	0.1164*
H142	0.9221	0.5675	0.8481	0.1164*
H152	1.3315	0.4125	0.8744	0.1398*
H151	1.2287	0.4273	0.9511	0.1404*
H153	1.2872	0.3096	0.9158	0.1402*
H311	0.8397	0.2847	0.5853	0.0628*
H312	0.7353	0.3527	0.5224	0.0619*
H302	0.8396	0.0566	0.5	0.0657*
H301	0.7368	0.1616	0.45	0.0654*
H281	0.6682	0.0588	0.6179	0.0507*
H241	0.8945	-0.0059	0.6788	0.0581*
H231	1.0103	0.0002	0.7769	0.0614*
H211	1.067	0.0925	0.9259	0.1241*
H213	1.1344	0.0478	0.8487	0.1245*
H212	0.9912	0.0098	0.8997	0.1244*
H271	0.6935	0.3109	0.8084	0.0782*
H261	0.575	0.3035	0.7126	0.0736*
H381	0.103	0.2132	0.634	0.1051*
H383	0.1667	0.3013	0.6617	0.1054*
H382	0.1928	0.2838	0.5798	0.1052*
H403	0.2585	0.0673	0.7127	0.1123*
H402	0.3329	0.1522	0.7373	0.1124*
H401	0.4529	0.0355	0.7048	0.1117*
H393	0.3006	0.0422	0.5824	0.1158*
H392	0.492	0.0122	0.5817	0.1163*
H391	0.4002	0.1108	0.5304	0.1165*
H342	1.4169	0.2748	0.3526	0.1109*

H341	1.3723	0.225	0.4297	0.1111*
H343	1.3235	0.1841	0.3653	0.1114*
H353	1.1899	0.4033	0.2935	0.1118*
H352	1.0086	0.4393	0.3364	0.1124*
H351	1.0912	0.315	0.3101	0.1121*
H362	1.2609	0.4696	0.3931	0.1359*
H361	1.2383	0.409	0.4685	0.1368*
H363	1.0814	0.4904	0.4361	0.1361*

Table 14. Atomic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2$) for compound 15.

	U^{11}	U^{22}	U^{33}	U^{12}	U^{13}	U^{23}
C1	0.081 (2)	0.067 (2)	0.064 (2)	-0.0212 (18)	-0.0214 (17)	-0.0216 (17)
C2	0.0420 (15)	0.0501 (17)	0.0357 (14)	-0.0183 (14)	-0.0057 (12)	-0.0036 (12)
C3	0.0518 (17)	0.0500 (18)	0.0505 (16)	-0.0004 (14)	-0.0208 (14)	-0.0070 (14)
C4	0.0533 (17)	0.0420 (16)	0.0534 (17)	-0.0006 (14)	-0.0173 (14)	-0.0117 (13)
C5	0.0359 (14)	0.0398 (15)	0.0383 (14)	-0.0122 (12)	-0.0036 (12)	-0.0017 (12)
C6	0.0451 (16)	0.0392 (16)	0.0457 (15)	-0.0124 (13)	-0.0135 (13)	0.0048 (13)
C7	0.0503 (16)	0.0345 (15)	0.0497 (16)	-0.0118 (13)	-0.0089 (14)	-0.0060 (13)
C8	0.0401 (15)	0.0384 (15)	0.0432 (15)	-0.0141 (12)	-0.0083 (12)	0.0013 (12)
C9	0.0442 (15)	0.0487 (17)	0.0411 (15)	-0.0204 (13)	-0.0064 (12)	-0.0015 (12)
C10	0.0455 (16)	0.0640 (18)	0.0428 (15)	-0.0225 (14)	-0.0128 (13)	0.0086 (14)
C11	0.0439 (16)	0.075 (2)	0.0453 (16)	-0.0285 (15)	-0.0115 (13)	0.0012 (14)
C12	0.0434 (17)	0.0537 (17)	0.0392 (15)	-0.0188 (14)	-0.0106 (14)	-0.0010 (13)
C13	0.0458 (16)	0.0620 (19)	0.0388 (15)	-0.0245 (14)	-0.0022 (13)	0.0089 (13)
C14	0.082 (2)	0.068 (2)	0.086 (2)	-0.0395 (19)	-0.0019 (19)	0.0039 (19)
C15	0.055 (2)	0.138 (3)	0.083 (2)	-0.048 (2)	-0.0137 (18)	0.025 (2)
C16	0.093 (3)	0.097 (3)	0.063 (2)	-0.043 (2)	0.0113 (19)	-0.0169 (19)
C17	0.0553 (18)	0.0566 (18)	0.0474 (16)	-0.0317 (15)	-0.0055 (14)	-0.0009 (14)
C18	0.080 (2)	0.083 (2)	0.066 (2)	-0.0457 (19)	0.0084 (18)	-0.0046 (18)
C19	0.095 (3)	0.064 (2)	0.076 (2)	-0.0443 (19)	-0.0157 (19)	-0.0070 (17)
C20	0.067 (2)	0.083 (2)	0.074 (2)	-0.0292 (18)	-0.0260 (17)	-0.0096 (18)
C21	0.086 (2)	0.083 (2)	0.070 (2)	-0.002 (2)	-0.0429 (19)	-0.0067 (18)
C22	0.0530 (17)	0.0479 (17)	0.0432 (15)	-0.0195 (14)	-0.0145 (13)	-0.0011 (13)
C23	0.0412 (15)	0.0417 (16)	0.0554 (17)	-0.0080 (13)	-0.0151 (13)	-0.0010 (13)
C24	0.0395 (15)	0.0418 (16)	0.0504 (16)	-0.0100 (13)	-0.0051 (13)	-0.0096 (13)
C25	0.0420 (15)	0.0342 (14)	0.0414 (14)	-0.0162 (13)	-0.0055 (12)	0.0018 (12)
C26	0.070 (2)	0.0358 (16)	0.0625 (18)	-0.0001 (14)	-0.0301 (16)	-0.0066 (14)
C27	0.076 (2)	0.0405 (17)	0.0678 (19)	-0.0001 (16)	-0.0325 (17)	-0.0170 (15)
C28	0.0393 (15)	0.0358 (14)	0.0425 (14)	-0.0138 (12)	-0.0063 (12)	-0.0031 (12)
C29	0.0396 (15)	0.0445 (16)	0.0472 (15)	-0.0183 (13)	-0.0067 (12)	-0.0025 (13)
C30	0.0618 (18)	0.0552 (18)	0.0455 (16)	-0.0338 (15)	-0.0019 (14)	-0.0095 (13)
C31	0.0521 (17)	0.0493 (17)	0.0442 (15)	-0.0234 (14)	0.0038 (13)	-0.0087 (13)
C32	0.0508 (17)	0.0488 (17)	0.0433 (16)	-0.0224 (14)	-0.0029 (14)	-0.0085 (14)

C33	0.0500 (17)	0.0594 (18)	0.0432 (15)	-0.0281 (15)	0.0079 (13)	-0.0033 (14)
C34	0.0524 (19)	0.084 (2)	0.077 (2)	-0.0263 (18)	0.0005 (16)	0.0112 (18)
C35	0.063 (2)	0.091 (3)	0.063 (2)	-0.0303 (19)	-0.0029 (16)	0.0078 (18)
C36	0.109 (3)	0.092 (3)	0.081 (2)	-0.073 (2)	0.018 (2)	-0.020 (2)
C37	0.0471 (16)	0.0571 (18)	0.0469 (16)	-0.0265 (15)	-0.0089 (13)	-0.0003 (13)
C38	0.0481 (18)	0.086 (2)	0.077 (2)	-0.0263 (17)	-0.0162 (16)	-0.0011 (18)
C39	0.093 (3)	0.072 (2)	0.079 (2)	-0.039 (2)	-0.0294 (19)	-0.0122 (18)
C40	0.069 (2)	0.093 (3)	0.063 (2)	-0.042 (2)	-0.0063 (17)	0.0162 (18)
O1	0.0667 (13)	0.0559 (12)	0.0545 (11)	-0.0141 (10)	-0.0231 (10)	-0.0112 (10)
O2	0.0600 (12)	0.0542 (12)	0.0585 (12)	-0.0230 (10)	0.0086 (10)	-0.0162 (10)
O3	0.0570 (12)	0.0795 (15)	0.0524 (12)	-0.0250 (11)	-0.0217 (10)	0.0193 (11)
O4	0.0447 (11)	0.0710 (13)	0.0414 (10)	-0.0281 (10)	-0.0115 (8)	0.0136 (9)
O5	0.0765 (14)	0.0621 (13)	0.0636 (13)	-0.0066 (11)	-0.0356 (11)	-0.0111 (10)
O6	0.0454 (11)	0.0656 (13)	0.0541 (11)	-0.0202 (10)	-0.0110 (9)	0.0184 (10)
O7	0.0744 (14)	0.0654 (13)	0.0557 (12)	-0.0327 (11)	0.0120 (10)	-0.0244 (11)
O8	0.0590 (12)	0.0602 (12)	0.0435 (10)	-0.0366 (10)	0.0103 (9)	-0.0125 (9)
N1	0.0504 (13)	0.0484 (14)	0.0415 (12)	-0.0201 (11)	-0.0057 (10)	-0.0049 (10)
N2	0.0440 (13)	0.0704 (16)	0.0413 (13)	-0.0271 (12)	-0.0140 (11)	0.0144 (12)
N3	0.0433 (13)	0.0472 (13)	0.0387 (12)	-0.0168 (11)	-0.0073 (10)	0.0000 (10)
N4	0.0552 (14)	0.0527 (14)	0.0460 (13)	-0.0312 (12)	0.0074 (11)	-0.0145 (11)

Table 10. Geometric parameters (Å, °) for compound 15.

C1—O1	1.425 (3)	C21—H211	0.977
C1—H11	0.986	C21—H213	0.992
C1—H13	0.983	C21—H212	0.984
C1—H12	0.993	C22—C23	1.372 (3)
C2—C3	1.383 (3)	C22—C27	1.385 (4)
C2—C7	1.376 (3)	C22—O5	1.372 (3)
C2—O1	1.372 (3)	C23—C24	1.381 (3)
C3—C4	1.379 (3)	C23—H231	0.967
C3—H31	0.971	C24—C25	1.370 (3)
C4—C5	1.391 (3)	C24—H241	0.978
C4—H41	0.966	C25—C26	1.384 (3)

C5—C6	1.370 (3)	C25—C28	1.505 (3)
C5—C8	1.501 (3)	C26—C27	1.376 (4)
C6—C7	1.384 (3)	C26—H261	0.971
C6—H61	0.967	C27—H271	0.963
C7—H71	0.965	C28—C29	1.532 (3)
C8—C9	1.530 (3)	C28—N3	1.495 (3)
C8—N1	1.502 (3)	C28—H281	1.03
C8—H81	1.029	C29—C30	1.535 (3)
C9—C10	1.535 (3)	C29—C31	1.538 (3)
C9—C11	1.535 (4)	C29—O6	1.440 (3)
C9—O2	1.434 (3)	C30—N4	1.470 (3)
C10—N2	1.468 (3)	C30—H302	1.004
C10—H101	1.001	C30—H301	1.008
C10—H102	1.012	C31—N4	1.467 (3)
C11—N2	1.468 (3)	C31—H311	1.003
C11—H112	1.005	C31—H312	1.011
C11—H111	1.007	C32—O7	1.216 (3)
C12—O3	1.219 (3)	C32—O8	1.343 (3)
C12—O4	1.337 (3)	C32—N4	1.348 (3)
C12—N2	1.337 (3)	C33—C34	1.506 (4)
C13—C14	1.507 (4)	C33—C35	1.511 (4)
C13—C15	1.511 (4)	C33—C36	1.519 (4)
C13—C16	1.501 (4)	C33—O8	1.479 (3)

C13—O4	1.479 (3)	C34—H342	0.978
C14—H141	0.978	C34—H341	0.972
C14—H143	0.983	C34—H343	0.98
C14—H142	0.984	C35—H353	0.977
C15—H152	0.966	C35—H352	0.974
C15—H151	0.978	C35—H351	0.977
C15—H153	0.975	C36—H362	0.967
C16—H162	0.974	C36—H361	0.973
C16—H161	0.977	C36—H363	0.974
C16—H163	0.97	C37—C38	1.520 (4)
C17—C18	1.519 (4)	C37—C39	1.519 (4)
C17—C19	1.529 (4)	C37—C40	1.525 (4)
C17—C20	1.526 (4)	C37—N3	1.488 (3)
C17—N1	1.490 (3)	C38—H381	0.972
C18—H183	0.982	C38—H383	0.984
C18—H182	0.987	C38—H382	0.98
C18—H181	0.984	C39—H393	0.976
C19—H192	0.973	C39—H392	0.978
C19—H193	0.975	C39—H391	0.982
C19—H191	0.973	C40—H403	0.973
C20—H202	0.977	C40—H402	0.981
C20—H201	0.991	C40—H401	0.987
C20—H203	0.982	O2—N1	1.501 (2)

C21—O5	1.424 (3)	O6—N3	1.500 (2)
<hr/>			
O1—C1—H11	107.3	C22—C23—C24	120.3 (2)
O1—C1—H13	109.1	C22—C23—H231	118.5
H11—C1—H13	110.1	C24—C23—H231	121.2
O1—C1—H12	109.7	C23—C24—C25	121.7 (2)
H11—C1—H12	110.9	C23—C24—H241	120.2
H13—C1—H12	109.7	C25—C24—H241	118.2
C3—C2—C7	119.5 (2)	C24—C25—C26	117.5 (2)
C3—C2—O1	115.8 (2)	C24—C25—C28	120.4 (2)
C7—C2—O1	124.6 (2)	C26—C25—C28	122.1 (2)
C2—C3—C4	119.6 (2)	C25—C26—C27	121.6 (2)
C2—C3—H31	119.5	C25—C26—H261	118.7
C4—C3—H31	120.9	C27—C26—H261	119.6
C3—C4—C5	121.8 (2)	C22—C27—C26	119.8 (2)
C3—C4—H41	119.6	C22—C27—H271	119.2
C5—C4—H41	118.7	C26—C27—H271	121
C4—C5—C6	117.3 (2)	C25—C28—C29	120.8 (2)
C4—C5—C8	122.4 (2)	C25—C28—N3	114.75 (19)
C6—C5—C8	120.4 (2)	C29—C28—N3	87.25 (17)
C5—C6—C7	122.1 (2)	C25—C28—H281	109.9
C5—C6—H61	118.4	C29—C28—H281	109.8
C7—C6—H61	119.5	N3—C28—H281	112.8
C6—C7—C2	119.8 (2)	C28—C29—C30	121.8 (2)

C6—C7—H71	120.8	C28—C29—C31	123.3 (2)
C2—C7—H71	119.5	C30—C29—C31	88.66 (18)
C5—C8—C9	120.5 (2)	C28—C29—O6	90.79 (17)
C5—C8—N1	114.2 (2)	C30—C29—O6	117.9 (2)
C9—C8—N1	87.44 (17)	C31—C29—O6	117.3 (2)
C5—C8—H81	109.7	C29—C30—N4	87.66 (18)
C9—C8—H81	110.3	C29—C30—H302	115.5
N1—C8—H81	113.3	N4—C30—H302	114.6
C8—C9—C10	124.5 (2)	C29—C30—H301	112.1
C8—C9—C11	120.8 (2)	N4—C30—H301	112.9
C10—C9—C11	88.48 (19)	H302—C30—H301	112
C8—C9—O2	91.35 (18)	C29—C31—N4	87.62 (18)
C10—C9—O2	116.5 (2)	C29—C31—H311	116.5
C11—C9—O2	118.1 (2)	N4—C31—H311	115.1
C9—C10—N2	88.11 (19)	C29—C31—H312	111.3
C9—C10—H101	114.8	N4—C31—H312	113.1
N2—C10—H101	115.3	H311—C31—H312	111.3
C9—C10—H102	110.7	O7—C32—O8	126.2 (2)
N2—C10—H102	114.3	O7—C32—N4	122.9 (2)
H101—C10—H102	111.7	O8—C32—N4	110.8 (2)
C9—C11—N2	88.10 (18)	C34—C33—C35	111.9 (2)
C9—C11—H112	115.9	C34—C33—C36	110.8 (3)
N2—C11—H112	114.2	C35—C33—C36	110.8 (3)
C9—C11—H111	111.1	C34—C33—O8	110.5 (2)
N2—C11—H111	114	C35—C33—O8	110.0 (2)
H112—C11—H111	111.6	C36—C33—O8	102.4 (2)
O3—C12—O4	125.9 (2)	C33—C34—H342	107.6
O3—C12—N2	122.9 (2)	C33—C34—H341	107.6
O4—C12—N2	111.2 (2)	H342—C34—H341	110.5
C14—C13—C15	110.4 (3)	C33—C34—H343	108.8
C14—C13—C16	112.1 (3)	H342—C34—H343	111.1
C15—C13—C16	111.8 (3)	H341—C34—H343	111
C14—C13—O4	110.0 (2)	C33—C35—H353	108.4
C15—C13—O4	101.9 (2)	C33—C35—H352	107.2
C16—C13—O4	110.2 (2)	H353—C35—H352	109.6
C13—C14—H141	107.4	C33—C35—H351	108.3
C13—C14—H143	108.2	H353—C35—H351	112.1
H141—C14—H143	110.6	H352—C35—H351	111.1
C13—C14—H142	109.6	C33—C36—H362	108.3

H141—C14—H142	110.9	C33—C36—H361	108.5
H143—C14—H142	110.2	H362—C36—H361	111.1
C13—C15—H152	109.5	C33—C36—H363	106.9
C13—C15—H151	108.5	H362—C36—H363	110.2
H152—C15—H151	110.6	H361—C36—H363	111.7
C13—C15—H153	106.6	C38—C37—C39	110.6 (2)
H152—C15—H153	110.2	C38—C37—C40	110.7 (2)
H151—C15—H153	111.4	C39—C37—C40	110.3 (3)
C13—C16—H162	108.4	C38—C37—N3	106.5 (2)
C13—C16—H161	107.2	C39—C37—N3	114.8 (2)
H162—C16—H161	111	C40—C37—N3	103.7 (2)
C13—C16—H163	108.5	C37—C38—H381	108.2
H162—C16—H163	111	C37—C38—H383	109.2
H161—C16—H163	110.6	H381—C38—H383	111
C18—C17—C19	111.1 (2)	C37—C38—H382	108.9
C18—C17—C20	110.9 (2)	H381—C38—H382	108.9
C19—C17—C20	110.5 (2)	H383—C38—H382	110.7
C18—C17—N1	104.0 (2)	C37—C39—H393	108.7
C19—C17—N1	105.8 (2)	C37—C39—H392	110.2
C20—C17—N1	114.3 (2)	H393—C39—H392	109.4
C17—C18—H183	109.2	C37—C39—H391	109.2
C17—C18—H182	108.4	H393—C39—H391	109.6
H183—C18—H182	110.7	H392—C39—H391	109.8
C17—C18—H181	108.6	C37—C40—H403	108.1
H183—C18—H181	109.6	C37—C40—H402	107.8
H182—C18—H181	110.4	H403—C40—H402	111.1
C17—C19—H192	108.1	C37—C40—H401	108.9
C17—C19—H193	109.9	H403—C40—H401	109.5
H192—C19—H193	110	H402—C40—H401	111.4
C17—C19—H191	108.3	C1—O1—C2	118.0 (2)
H192—C19—H191	110	C9—O2—N1	91.11 (15)
H193—C19—H191	110.4	C13—O4—C12	120.62 (19)
C17—C20—H202	106	C21—O5—C22	117.8 (2)
C17—C20—H201	110.2	C29—O6—N3	90.51 (16)
H202—C20—H201	110.7	C33—O8—C32	120.92 (19)
C17—C20—H203	107.6	C8—N1—O2	89.90 (16)
H202—C20—H203	110.7	C8—N1—C17	116.6 (2)
H201—C20—H203	111.4	O2—N1—C17	108.54 (17)
O5—C21—H211	107.3	C10—N2—C11	93.69 (19)
O5—C21—H213	109	C10—N2—C12	130.4 (2)
H211—C21—H213	110.4	C11—N2—C12	124.6 (2)
O5—C21—H212	108.5	O6—N3—C28	89.95 (15)
H211—C21—H212	110.4	O6—N3—C37	109.43 (17)
H213—C21—H212	111.1	C28—N3—C37	117.53 (19)
C23—C22—C27	119.0 (2)	C30—N4—C31	93.96 (18)
C23—C22—O5	125.0 (2)	C30—N4—C32	124.5 (2)
C27—C22—O5	116.0 (2)	C31—N4—C32	129.7 (2)

Fig 6. The asymmetric unit of compound **15** with labeling scheme and 50% probability ellipsoids. For the sake of clarity, the labels of hydrogen atoms are not represented.

Fig 7. 3D-packing viewed down the *a* axis for compound **15**.

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